

Choice and Fidelity

A Beginner's Antidote to
Unconscious Materialism

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Introduction

Christians know that there are more things in heaven and earth than blind chance and deterministic laws of nature – what Jacques Monod summed up as “chance and necessity.” But after several centuries in which the materialist way of looking at the world has dominated our culture, most of us have been caught up in that worldview enough to sit uneasily between it and the Bible’s teaching. People educated in science sometimes feel this most keenly.

It can make our thinking inconsistent, cause us to misunderstand Scripture, and generate doubts about our faith which are more to do with a false underlying view of the world than any weakness in the evidence for Christianity.

This book is intended to help us “think through our thinking” at the most fundamental level, but in the simplest way I can contrive. It uncovers some of the inherent weaknesses in the way we may see the Creation, which we have absorbed unconsciously from our education and our culture.

Its subject is, actually, the deeper issues of philosophy and metaphysics, but I’m not going to tell you that in case you think it’s obscure and difficult. In fact I’ve tried to keep things as uncomplicated as I can because these questions should interest us all, and they certainly affect the discipleship of us all. I try to explain any specialized words in case you come across them elsewhere, and I have avoided footnotes and detailed sources to make life easier. I hope the arguments speak for themselves, even when I have filched them from better thinkers than myself.

In the end the issue is quite simple: the materialist foundations of the world, that is chance and necessity, are built on sand, and we understand a lot more about reality, and a lot more easily, if they are replaced altogether. The God we worship is the underlying cause of things: the world actually runs on choice and fidelity.

1 Blinded by the View

“To a man with a hammer, everything looks like a nail.”

Mark Twain

Lessons from seafarers

The story of how the scourge of scurvy amongst sailors came to be cured with fresh fruit and vegetables is often told, though it is usually grossly oversimplified, like most scientific myth-making about pioneers from Copernicus to Darwin. From the time of the great early explorers like Magellan through to the nineteenth century, ship-owners budgeted for 50% mortality from scurvy on long sea voyages. Wars, perhaps even empires, were won and lost because of the disease.

According to the account given in books celebrating the triumphs of science, a ship's surgeon named James Lind found in 1747 that citrus fruit cured scurvy, his discovery leading eventually to the issuing of lime-juice to British sailors and finally to the isolation of Vitamin C and understanding of its function.

The story is actually far murkier, and more instructive than that. For although Lind wrote an extensive treatise on scurvy, and referred at length to those who believed that fresh fruit and vegetables cured it, he actually downplayed their opinions, including even his own earlier successful cure of a sailor using citrus fruit. Instead, in the book he favoured his preferred holistic theory about the disease (which was quite wrong).

If I may over-simplify the history, those who noticed the benefits of fresh fruit and vegetables tended to be sea captains or heterodox doctors making empirical observations. In at least one case, they got the idea from primitive natives who offered the bark and leaves of a particular plant as a cure for some stranded sailors. These successes were reported intermittently over several centuries. Those dismissing such anecdotal accounts were the professional physicians trained in the holistic theory of medicine known as the theory of humours. Essentially, the fresh food hypothesis couldn't be made to fit the accepted theory, and so it was, after careful consideration, rejected by those with the greatest expertise.

My point here is not to wave the flag for empirical science against hidebound tradition. The professionals were *doing* empirical science, but they were doing so under the umbrella of a particular philosophical worldview, held largely unconsciously.

For the theory of humours was not simply a way of doing medicine. Scientific medicine had retained, from an increasingly rejected Aristotelian system, the idea that matter consists of various combinations of the four elements (fire, air, earth and water), and that this is reflected in the human body in the combination of the four humours: blood, black bile, yellow bile and phlegm. The theory of humours dated back to Hippocrates in the fifth century BC, but humours were simply seen as part of the broader way the world worked. They were a conclusion from higher level concepts, accepted as axiomatically as the existence of atoms is now (and indeed was in Lind's time). No doctor then or now would dream of suggesting that anything in medicine casts doubt on atomic physics.

Thus most physicians involved in research were doing what the philosopher of science Thomas Kuhn has called “normal science,” which means applying the accepted global paradigm (in this case the theory of humours within a theory of everything) to particular areas of research. Normal science does not challenge the underlying paradigm: fundamental change always comes from outliers thinking in new ways, like Bacon, Copernicus or Einstein.

Occasional mavericks like the heretical physician Johannes Bachstrom, who well before Lind was utterly convinced that scurvy was entirely due to a deficiency of fresh fruit and vegetables, were rejected because they were operating outside the accepted philosophical paradigm. The sea-captains with their anecdotal stories of cure were simply ignorant science-deniers who, nowadays, would be cancelled from *Facebook* and *YouTube*, still less be asked to speak at scientific conferences.

The fact that the outliers turned out to be right was not simply because of the progress of science – though in the end empirical truth forced a shift in the paradigm. Although ushering in a new idea of nutritional medicine, in some ways the dietary hypothesis of scurvy as vitamin C deficiency was a return to an older worldview pre-dating even Hippocrates, in which particular foods had health value. That at least would seem to be the implication of what lay behind the thinking of the natives who knew that scurvy sailors needed their particular kind of bark and leaves, rather than the rebalancing of their humoral tempers.

But I have omitted a more modern episode in the story of scurvy and worldviews which never gets mentioned in the “triumph of science” myth. For Lind and naval lime-juice notwithstanding, even on Captain Scott’s Antarctic expedition in 1911, one of the expedition’s doctors gave a lecture on scurvy explaining the prevalent theory that it was caused by bacterial contamination of food. The Germ Theory of disease had become the prevalent wisdom in the second half of the nineteenth century, and so once again the paradigm trumped the evidence of a couple of centuries or more.

Unfortunately, the careful application of the theory to the canned meat on the expedition did not prevent Scott’s men getting scurvy, nor its rampant course amongst the troops at Gallipoli, arguably contributing to their tragic failure.

It was not until 1927 that dietary deficiency as the cause of scurvy was finally established by the isolation of ascorbic acid. Its discoverer, Albert Szent-Györgi, reminiscent of Kuhn, regarded scientific progress to be the work of scientific dissenters, relying on intuition instead of established paradigms. “*A discovery must be, by definition, at variance with existing knowledge,*” he wrote in 1972.

One important lesson to learn from this is that, contrary to myth, human knowledge does not progress steadily, but often becomes stagnated for long periods, or even moves backwards, because the underlying assumptions of the educated intellectuals are wrong. Sometimes it is even old and long-discarded ideas, rather than revolutionary new concepts, that turn out to be better.

Lessons from pandemics

The selective blindness produced by worldviews and, more specifically medical paradigms, has not gone away. I was trained at medical school in the germ theory of disease, which was what largely replaced the theory of humours in the microscopic age. Parasites, bacteria, viruses and prions were progressively tinier “germs” discovered by increasingly sophisticated means. They were responsible for much disease, and their destruction became the focus of medical endeavour.

Germ theory was combined with the molecular theory of therapeutics, maintaining that most diseases need a magic bullet molecule developed (and patented!) by pharmaceutical corporations. The latter has over the last decade or two, for a variety of reasons ideological, political and corporate, focused especially on magic bullet vaccines. The story of how molecular medicine was shoehorned into the universities and the medical profession by the moneyed “philanthropic” interests of John D. Rockefeller through the *Rockefeller Foundation*, and how vaccine-centred medicine was likewise promoted by the not dissimilar *Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation*, is important but seldom explored.

Early in my medical career, though, I realised that I had been taught absolutely nothing about my regular observation in the surgery that people who are stressed or fatigued tend to catch the virus infections that are circulating, and the happier souls are often spared. This is still a neglected area, but is certainly a significant factor for health. The germs themselves are far from being the whole story. In fact we have only just begun to escape germ theory sufficiently to understand that the well-being of our “microbiome” is a keystone of health – almost 50% of our cells are non-human. And the role of our “virome,” consisting in some estimates of 380 trillion individual viruses, is not only more complicated in disease than we have assumed, but undoubtedly plays a barely-explored part in maintaining health. RNA viruses appear to be responsible for 8% of human genetic material, not to mention that which has become permanently incorporated into our genomic function. This makes the danger of any individual virus far from a straightforward matter.

Fast-forward to 2020 and the COVID-19 pandemic. Because of the prevailing scientific paradigm, with its focus on detecting the presence of viruses or virus fragments (regardless of actual disease) and on producing novel vaccines for profit, the importance of another vitamin, Vitamin D, has been sidelined just as much as Vitamin C ever was for scurvy.

There are now multiple good studies suggesting that high-dose Vitamin D massively reduces the incidence and severity of COVID-19, and conversely that low Vitamin D levels are a predictor of poorer outcomes. This effect is not specific to SARS-CoV-2, research papers from several years ago confirming its benefit during influenza outbreaks. Furthermore it is cheap, safe and readily available. It may be effective enough, particularly when supplemented by off-patent drugs, to render the expense and incompletely known risks of mRNA vaccines unnecessary.

There is good logic behind its role. Vitamin D, synthesized by sunlight on the skin, is particularly deficient in the elderly frail who stay inside and tend not to eat well. This is also the group most at risk from winter viruses. Vitamin D has well-known functions within the immune system.

And yet not only have medical authorities and governments worldwide shown little interest in the possibility that Vitamin D is of value, but they have actively censored and castigated those advocating it – an anti-scientific situation that never occurred with respect to scurvy in the “bad old days.” When Vitamin D has been mentioned at all by “official” organs, the dosage recommended has been that used with respect to its activity in bone (based on its role in preventing rickets), rather than looking at the higher doses suggested by research on its separate role in immunity.

These two examples from the world of vitamins are intended to show how theoretical models can prevent us seeing obvious truths, in some cases for centuries. But the subject of this book is not individual theories, but rather the broad worldviews in which they are embedded, the big ideas that govern how we see the world, and which therefore frame the theories the world’s scientists have about individual parts of it.

In particular I want to examine what it is about our prevalent worldview today that makes a robust belief in the God of the Bible either difficult to hold, or only easy to hold in a diluted way. I am asking you to shift that worldview, in your own mind, in a very fundamental way.

The particular concepts I will focus on are those of chance and necessity, both of which I shall suggest to be doubtful categories well overdue for replacement. Fortunately, as far as I can tell, although their abandonment makes things of vital importance to us, such as God and our own conscious minds, less problematic, it is of no detriment whatsoever to other important areas like science. Indeed, I suggest that my proposal brings science and faith far closer together – though only at the expense of the materialistic worldview that often *masquerades* as science.

2 Choice and Fidelity

We must believe in free will. We have no choice.

Isaac Bashevis Singer

A book denying purpose

In 1971 the biochemist Jacques Monod wrote an influential book entitled *Chance and Necessity*, of which the most lasting contribution was to explain the appearance of purpose in living things, and particularly within evolution, in natural terms.

We immediately hit a significant problem there, if we ask ourselves just what that world “natural” means, but that question is for later in the present book.

The classical philosophical term for “purpose,” or to be more precise “final cause,” is *teleology*, to which Monod responded by coining the new word *teleonomy*. The derivation of his word is the combination of Greek *telos* (end or purpose) and *nomos* (law), which captures the idea that some kind of laws – in this case the laws of nature – are ultimately behind what only *appears* purposeful in the world. Choice, wherever it seems to appear in the world, is actually an illusion that can be reduced to the laws of nature.

The title of the book, according to Monod, was a quotation from the Greek philosopher Democritus:

Everything existing in the universe is the fruit of chance and necessity.

If we think of his book in its cultural context we see that its real intention is to *explain away* teleology by reducing it to two “givens,” that is to chance and necessity. Chance and necessity are indisputable, it implies, and can actually explain what only *appears* to be purpose. The book also assumes that its readers would *want* to explain purposiveness, or choice, away. This latter point is rather less obvious, because the cultural context has not changed that much, and the educated world still prefers material explanations to those that seem “metaphysical.” The book *seems* just to be presenting the implications of accepted scientific truth.

The book also assumes that there is no question about the existence of chance and necessity themselves. But in fact, both terms, when examined more closely, pose a great number of problems.

The purpose of this book

The purpose of *this* book is to point some of these problems out, rather than to puzzle about whether the book itself only *appears* to have a purpose instead of being the product of mere chance and necessity!

Once one considers even the possibility that one might not be able to take chance and necessity, as fundamental causes, for granted, then everything changes. Although it is true that one *can* find arguments to reduce “choice” to randomness or laws of nature, whether dealing with human, animal, or divine choice, yet it is equally true that one can reduce chance and necessity to choice. It is no more rational to assume the existence of chance and necessity without evidence than it is to believe in God and the human will.

This *impasse* is, in essence, the age-old argument between philosophers like Democritus and Epicurus, who believed that, under the right circumstances, the universe would organize itself undirected, and their opponents like Plato or Aristotle who believed that a purposeful universe is both more intuitive and more rational.

I have no intention of trying to settle that argument by philosophical reasoning here, though I will certainly emphasize that both are equally faith positions. It is easy to think of teleology, in nature at any rate, as requiring faith in a God or gods. But because we live in the shadow of the scientific Enlightenment, it is less easy to see that Monod's position is the result of a particular belief system, materialism, which is essentially Epicureanism rebranded. Worldviews are notoriously invisible to those who possess them.

However, one can recognize this stark dichotomy of thought more clearly using an example from the Intelligent Design Movement, whose principal aim is to show that the scientific evidence in nature is more compatible with design than with chance and necessity alone. Whether this approach is successful or unsuccessful is not my concern here.

Mathematician William Dembski's approach to ID has been to derive a "universal probability bound" from estimations of the total number of events, down to the quantum level, that have ever occurred in the entire universe. Strange as it may seem to most of us, this is not an impossible task, although not surprisingly different people's estimates vary quite a lot.

As the second stage of his argument, Dembski has calculated the probability of amino acids spontaneously combining to form the simplest functional protein thought necessary for life. He arrives at a probability that is orders of magnitude lower than his universal probability bound, that is, far less than one chance in the entire number of events that have ever occurred anywhere. The universe would have to be many orders of magnitude bigger ("orders of magnitude" corresponding to X_{10} , X_{100} , X_{1000} etc) to expect such an event to happen even once by chance. This, he concludes, makes design the preferred explanation for this protein.

But the Epicurean opponents of ID do not see this as a problem. Nobody really argues about the universal probability bound itself, other than minor quibbling about its actual value. To deal with the vanishingly low probability of the protein synthesis, some critics have said that there simply must be law-like natural processes behind the organization of this first protein, although they are not yet known, and perhaps were only even possible in the lost past.

Chance, in other words, is in this case actually an unknown necessity. When we come to explore the nature of chance, we will see that this is actually incoherent, but here's a quick spoiler: chance is *defined* in science as events whose exact causes are not known. You can't simply wave necessary causes into existence to make chance disappear. Unless you *know* the cause, in science the unknown cause is chance *by definition*. And that being the case you cannot evade grappling with the issue of low probability.

A few, like the molecular biologist Eugene Koonin, take the low probability as evidence that a multiverse must exist, radically increasing the total number of events and therefore the chance of any one event happening. But in fact unless these multiple universes could communicate with each other (in which case we would probably know about them) their bare existence would be irrelevant to probability. Pigs are no more likely to fly on a desert island simply because there are many such isolated islands in the world. You are just as unlikely to toss 100 "heads" in a row in populous New York as in a hermit's cell on a rock in the Atlantic Ocean.

Most critics of Dembski, however, simply reply that unique, and therefore extremely low probability events, are seen to happen all the time, and that the existence of proteins simply shows that, at some stage in the earth's history, such a chance event has happened. And that cannot be refuted, because it is based on a belief about reality, not on any evidence.

It is certainly equally true that to attribute anything in the world – not just the existence of proteins – to deliberate agency is a matter of belief, not proof. But that is simply to put both positions on an equal footing. And that explains why both ateleological and teleological systems have been arguing with each other since at least the time of the Greek philosophers.

As I mentioned above, I do not wish to settle that long running dispute here. My aim instead is to speak primarily to those who, for other reasons, already believe in God, and in particular the purposeful and active *theistic* God of the Bible. Others may well find my book helpful in understanding some of the issues in the dispute. My purpose is to try and resolve the confusion in the minds of most modern Christians – and particularly those involved in any way in the sciences – who have been conditioned to try and live within both systems, the Epicurean and the Theistic, at the same time.

This is obviously possible, because people do it in their millions. But it is ultimately not a good idea because the systems are actually incompatible. Just as you could worship at the Jerusalem temple on the Sabbath, and offer your child to Chemosh on Monday, so you can believe in the Living God and still conceive of nature as governed by chance and necessity. But the contradiction will eventually catch up with you. In fact, chance and necessity, in Monod's sense, cannot (in my view) even *exist* in the same universe as the God of the Bible.

If the Universe is governed by chance and necessity, there is really no place for God – which is why historically Deism, the belief that God has set up a self-contained “clockwork” creation, has always tended to become atheism. Conversely, if the creation is governed by God's will, there is no room for chance (in Monod's sense – we will have to define chance better to see its valid role in a Christian worldview), and there is no room for necessity, because it will be seen to be merely what God has willed to happen regularly, through his faithfulness to the creation.

Surprisingly then, or so I will argue, we have to make a choice between only two possible worlds. Either, by the impersonal forces of chance and necessity, we will *seem* to choose to believe in a world of chance and necessity. Or we will genuinely choose to believe in a world of choice and fidelity.

3 Causes

Elijah came near to all the people and said, “How long will you hesitate between two opinions? If the Lord is God, follow Him; but if Baal, follow him.” But the people did not answer him a word.

1 Kings 18:21

Every cause in one chapter

Until you take time to think about it, you don't appreciate that there are remarkably few categories of possible cause for events in the world. This is true whether you are thinking generally, or a bit more specifically in terms of science. This chapter is about the general nature of causes, or what you might call the philosophical, or metaphysical, level if you like long words.

At the level of philosophy there are only three basic reasons that stuff happens, and we have already come across them in the previous chapter. These are:

1 Necessity

In relative terms some things simply have to happen. Two massive objects *will* be attracted by gravity, and unless someone invents an anti-gravity device, that will be true across the universe and at all times, as far as we know. The mutual attraction of massive objects is therefore *necessary*. But that does not mean that the law of gravity itself *had* to exist in the universe, or even that the universe itself had to exist. Either of these might be absolutely inevitable, but it can't be proved. The closer you come to considering *absolute* necessity, the more you are dependent on faith, rather than evidence.

Perhaps, says the Epicurean, the universe simply has to exist, out of necessity. No, says the theist, God is the necessary, uncaused, being on whom the existence of the universe depends. Both cannot be true. There may, in fact, be good reasons to argue for one of these necessities over the other, though someone like Aristotle is your man for that, rather than me. My point is simply to say that for most people some element of necessity, either of the universe itself or of God, lies at the back of the cosmos, which makes the other apparently necessary causes around us, such as gravitational laws, inevitable only in a secondary way.

Not many people argue that the universe exists by chance, because that is generally considered to be an irrational position. Recently, though, at least one cosmologist, Lawrence Krauss, has argued that the universe came into existence from nothing through chance fluctuations in a quantum vacuum. He made no real attempt, though, to explain whether this quantum vacuum, or the fact that it is supposed to fluctuate, also came into existence by chance. The quantum vacuum would seem instead in this proposal to be the *necessary* foundation on which chance built, and that assumption undermines the whole point of the claim that the universe and everything in it exist by chance.

For modern scientists, it is more or less taken for granted that the laws of nature are the necessary foundation of the world we see, because science is all about discovering these laws and how they work. The cause of those laws themselves is therefore not even a scientific question. Those laws themselves depend on the various cosmological constants that can be calculated and which, as far as we can tell, themselves have no particular reason to possess the values they do.

You have no doubt heard of the cosmological fine tuning arguments for God, which say that the arbitrary values of the several fundamental constants we know suggest they have been chosen deliberately, presumably by God. Had they other values, even by absurdly tiny amounts, the cosmos could not exist as it does.

Apparent fine tuning at various levels from the characteristics of water to carbon chemistry have intrigued serious scientists for well over a century. The (agnostic) astronomer Fred Hoyle, back in 1982, wrote:

A common sense interpretation of the facts suggests that a super-intellect has monkeyed with physics, as well as with chemistry and biology, and that there are no blind forces worth speaking about in nature.

The Epicurean can always, however, reply that the constants are either simply necessary – brute facts – or that they have their particular values by chance. We exist, therefore we got lucky.

Speaking *scientifically*, the opposing claims of deliberate fine tuning or undetermined fine tuning are no better than each other, for science can only properly draw inferences from what it actually observes, which are the events produced by these cosmological constants through the laws they appear to govern. Anything beyond the physical realm is not science but a belief, and the reasons for the constants are apparently beyond the physical realm. Once again, we see that in the matter of origins, at least, chance and necessity are matters of belief.

But, on the other hand, if choice exists behind the workings of the universe, that is, if the universe is God's purposeful creation (which admittedly is itself a belief), it follows that any "necessity" we find is only relative, and is in fact an expression of divine choice, not a cause of it.

To use a human analogy, if efficient border guards shoot everyone trying to escape from a totalitarian country, then relatively speaking, death is a necessary result of fleeing. But in point of fact, in every case death is more fundamentally caused by the choice of the border guards to obey the choice of the dictator. It might be of practical value for disgruntled citizens, and certainly achieves the aims of the dictator, if they see the connection between escape and death as inevitable, for self-preservation. But at some point in history overturning the choice of the dictatorship will also destroy the illusion of its necessity. Choice can produce necessity as an effect – but it is harder to see how necessity can produce choice.

2 Chance

The Epicurean concept of chance is that some events occur that, ultimately, have no rational cause. That is another way of saying they generate themselves without depending on what has gone before.

To speak of chance as a cause has therefore long been recognized by careful thinkers to be an oxymoron. Causelessness simply cannot be a cause, any more than noiselessness is a noise. It becomes very difficult for most people to get their heads round such a "causeless" concept of chance once they face up squarely to what it means. In stories of magic a palace might appear out of thin air, but in our mind there is always the thought that some wizard's esoteric skills willed it to happen, or at a pinch that at least in fantasy worlds the laws of nature might produce such phenomena. But in both of those cases chance is an effect of something else, a choice or a necessity, and is not itself a cause.

If “chance” were truly causeless, then it would cause absolutely anything, at any time, anywhere, without restraint by other causes. The appearance of palaces out of thin air should be as common as point mutations in the SARS-CoV-2 virus. This does not seem to be the case!

Not many people are willing to believe that the universe poofed into existence one day by sheer chance. Indeed, the anti-religious skeptic will often use the argument that to believe that even *God* poofed the universe into existence is absurd. Such a belief in *ex nihilo* creation may, of course, be wrong, but it is not absurd: it assumes a creative will as the First Cause, and we know that our own wills make new and interesting things happen all the time. Creation *ex nihilo* is not in our skill-set, but plausibly it could be in God’s.

But to suggest that the universe exists by chance is to suggest that the first causeless event created the ultimate orderly system, the cosmos, including all the rational causes since operating within it. Yet we have to go on to believe that causelessness immediately lost its mojo and became the generally disruptive thing we know as chance today. Palaces, or anything like them, have never been seen to pop into existence. Randomness does not obviously make interesting things happen now – why should we believe it did in the beginning?

In proper science, “chance” or “randomness” has a different and more limited meaning, which is entirely to do with *human ignorance* of causes that are actually assumed to be necessary, that is to say they are governed by the laws of nature. There are actually very few candidates for “causelessness” in the natural world, and they prove to be of little explanatory power on close examination. I’ll return to them in a later chapter.

Even many real scientists are thoroughly muddled about the vital distinction between these two concepts of chance, which in academic-speak are called “ontological randomness” (that is a lack of cause) and “epistemological randomness” (that is our lack of knowledge about cause). We’ll explore this later, too.

3 Choice

Our entire experience of the world is as conscious, volitional beings. That is to say, a huge proportion of our life is about making choices, or suffering the choices of others whom we know to be conscious, volitional beings too (unless we descend into the insanity of solipsism and believe that everybody else is a figment of our imagination). We know somewhat less about the free-will of the dog that bites us as we pass the neighbour’s house, or the bird that takes food from our hand, but our natural impulse is to attribute some analogy of choice to them, even as we recognize they lack our rationality. We have to screw up our eyes to see the friendly playfulness of a dolphin as purely the interaction of chemical necessity or some undefined kind of chance. We virtually have to pull our eyes out of their sockets to view our own consciousness in that way.

The book *Chance and Necessity* is itself a typical example of the conundrum faced by all Epicureans when they try to deny the reality of choice. For through the book Monod is trying, by rational argument, to get his readers to change their ideas, to make different choices about how they view and deal with the world. More than that, we know that Monod chose to write the book, for the good of the world or to make money or a reputation, and then made many hundreds of subsequent choices about how best to present his thoughts once he had settled that first decision. No doubt (like all purveyors of ideas) he blamed readers who failed to understand, or chose to contradict, his thesis.

It may, of course, be quite true that all our decisions are downstream of necessary laws or mere chance, but books making that argument require that we deny it in practice by their very existence. Paradoxically, few would adopt such ideas without being persuaded by the arguments in the books.

One reason it is deceptively easy to theorise about the illusory nature of “free choice” is that, like consciousness itself, the human will is entirely subjective. “I choose,” irreducibly, as “me.” As soon as we begin to examine choice in the abstract as an object, it begins to appear to be a negotiable truth, and plausible arguments can be made for putting it all down to brain chemistry or whatever.

But the will is not actually an “it” to be understood – it is non-negotiably an “I” which goes about its business of making choices regardless of our theories. You cannot treat the existence of subjective experience objectively. Or if you try, you will forget what it actually is. That is why not even the most reductive materialists live by their theories about the illusion of free-will: in fact they are nearly always academics making their living by writing books intended to change our minds.

It follows that one simply cannot discuss “choice” as a cause in the same “objective” way one discusses chance or necessity. Instead, “I” must decide whether I believe that another “I” (or maybe more than one) is causing events in the world, or even causing the world itself. In the case of other human beings, the surest way to decide is not to look at the events, but to encounter the person causing them.

Logically, then, the same applies when it comes to personal agency behind nature. We believe in God because we come to recognize a superior *subjective* will operating analogously to ours, rather than by analyzing the events in the world objectively. It is the same process by which virtually everybody believes in the agency of other people rather than in solipsism.

If we take this path the critic will say that our subjective religious belief, rather than dispassionate science, has determined our worldview. And this might be a problem if it were not for the fact that it is *always* our subjective judgement that determines our view of nature. The attempt to take the “view from nowhere” in science is a useful fiction that helps nature speak for itself. But even in science we can never escape being “I,” and neither should we wish to.

These three philosophical categories – necessity, chance and choice – encompass all the causes there are! The world is not as complicated as we might have thought. In fact, given that we need to make a fundamental choice between two worldviews (if my arguments hold), we’ll end up jettisoning at least one of those categories. If we ignore more esoteric possibilities (and humans are always able to think up esoteric possibilities, such as pan-psychism where the whole universe contributes to consciousness more or less unconsciously), we will either come to believe in a universe ruled by chance and necessity, or in a universe ruled by conscious choices which are either habitual (which I will call “fidelity”) or occasional (more readily understood as choice). The choice is yours.

4 A Brief History of Causation

*Why, oh why, oh why oh, why?
Why, oh why, oh why?
Because because because because
Goodbye goodbye goodbye*

Woody Guthrie

Early man

It will be useful at this point to spend some time considering how our beliefs about causation have developed down the ages. This helps us to see how much of our worldview is taken for granted by absorption, rather than demonstrated to be true.

We obviously cannot know now how the first rational people thought the world worked. But it is a fair bet, based on the most ancient literature and on primitive societies today, that conscious agents of choice were believed to be behind everything. Perhaps things in nature were attributed to ancestral spirits, or demons, or perhaps (as I suggest in my book *The Generations of Heaven and Earth*) people before Adam were endowed with a sense of the heavenly Father-God who caused everything.

We have grown accustomed to thinking of such ideas as “primitive,” but given what I have said about the equally faith-based nature of Epicureanism and theism, we would do better to examine both on their merits. Certainly, to extrapolate our own ability to make choices to the operations of the world made clear sense to our ancestors.

It is not true to say, though, that science disproves this “animistic” view, because as Assyriologist Francesca Rochberg has written (in *Before Nature*), the ancient Babylonians had an effective system of science that lasted two millennia and still informs our own science, without even having a concept of “nature.”

In their system, the gods (as volitional beings) decreed all that would happen in the world. They communicated these decrees to mankind in the form of omens, astronomical events or dreams. It is not entirely clear how this was thought to operate in a material sense, simply because the Babylonians were not that interested in material causes. There seems to have been at least an element of the idea that the visible world responded to the gods in some kind of “sympathetic” way, rather than simply that the gods sent a comet or a set of liver omens into the material world as a medium of communication.

Another example, from Egyptian cosmology, can help us to understand this. You can find many pictures on the internet of Egyptian coffin paintings, in which the sky-goddess Nut arches over the earth god Geb, held up by the air god Shu, and so on. This leads materialistically minded people nowadays to say either that the Egyptians “represented” material nature using divine imagery, or that the Egyptians “really” thought the sky was solid, and pictured this false science in anthropomorphic ways.

Neither is in fact likely – the Egyptians believed that the sky, the air and the earth *were* divinities, who manifested themselves to mankind as material things. In that case, an earthquake was Geb deciding to shake, astral phenomena were Nut strutting her stuff, and so on.

If we are to understand the ancient mindset, we are required to make the same kind of mental shift we make for those optical illusions that can be viewed in two incompatible ways, as a duck and a rabbit, or as a beauty and an old crone. To moderns the real world is one of materials, behind which there may, perhaps, lie a nebulous spiritual world. To the Egyptians, the real world was a world of divine agents, manifested through a nebulous material world. Their basic assumptions have never been proven wrong!

Chance or necessity, then, were irrelevant to the ancients except insofar as, in a polytheistic system, gods might not know what other gods would do and so be subject to “chance,” and as they were part of the cosmos (indeed, they *were* the cosmos) they seem to have arisen in some involuntary way from the primaevial chaos through “necessity.” Ancient peoples appear to have given up theorizing beyond that point of “brute fact.”

The Hebrew God

The strict monotheism of Israel requires a re-think of the cosmologies I have been discussing. For by setting Yahweh as the eternal God over and above his creation, he clearly can't *be* the elements of nature in the way the pagan gods were. This, if you think about it, gives a much clearer conceptual basis for considering the universe as a single created system, but the Hebrew Bible doesn't go that far. Instead it describes the world as people experience it – as a layer-cake of realms of indeterminate extent, between the heavens and the earth, the extremes from which the Creation in between is named.

The Bible does, however, see God as the king whose choices govern all the things he has made, and so divine choice is still behind all the events in nature – although to use the term “nature” is itself an anachronism, because that very term, invented later by the Greeks, implies such a single system.

It is amazing how easily we unconsciously disenchant this God-directed creation as we read the Bible, perhaps accepting that God sometimes rules scriptural events by interfering “miraculously,” whilst we assume that most of the time the laws of nature were left to themselves. We may even surmise that the unusual events described in the Bible were actually just primitive interpretations of natural phenomena happening to occur at just the right time.

This is to misunderstand the Bible's worldview. Like the pagans, the Israelites believed that personal agency was behind *everything*. Not that God was the sole agent, although he was the supreme one in all things: a multitude of angels did his bidding, some bringing evil rather than good; human beings were volitional agents, although subject to the overarching will of God; and even the animals are attributed with the same limited purposeful agency that we ourselves customarily attribute to them (see for example the whole of Psalm 104).

There are hints that the elements of nature – which are strictly treated as creatures, never as divinities – operate as it were autonomously “under licence” from God. Job 38:33 even refers to the “laws [*chuqqah*] of the heavens” that govern the stars. But we should not necessarily equate these with “laws of nature” as it is possible that the heavenly bodies were considered to be living beings choosing to obey a divine decree, rather than as inanimate objects following scientific rules. C. S. Lewis played with such an idea in the character of the personal Star in *The Voyage of the Dawn Treader*, consciously challenging the scientific dis-enchantment of nature in seeing stars as merely “huge balls of burning gas.” Even if such personification is not the Bible's intent, the imagery of “laws” may have been a purely poetic analogy in Job.

It is important for my thesis that we grasp that a world ruled by sovereign divine choice does not necessarily entail caprice and confusion as is often objected, certainly no more than one ruled by chance and necessity does. In fact, monotheism allows for an orderly universe, directed by one unrivalled will, which no polytheistic system can, nor the dualism of chance and necessity.

When Yahweh is praised in Scripture for sending the rains in due season, or for creating the heavenly bodies to mark the seasons, it is because these things are attributed to his fidelity towards creation. The ancient Hebrews didn't do science, of course, but in theory one could study astronomy, say, as readily and exactly under the concept, "This is how God habitually works," as under "This is how the laws of gravity habitually work." If the maths still works, the maths still works.

The Greeks

It was the genius of the Greek thinkers to question everything, even the gods – though with a pantheon as corrupt as theirs such questioning was perhaps unavoidable. All kinds of radically new ideas came from them, which we now take for granted. Democritus's replacement of the gods with chance we have already come across.

The Greeks also hit on the idea of treating all-that-exists as a single being, a "cosmos," in which everything affects everything else as an interactive system, as in the human body. Such a concept, though obvious to us, is not self-evident from living in the world. This cosmos would originally contain the gods, if they existed, as well. But for some thinkers the idea enabled the conception of a divine world entirely separate from the one we know, such as Plato's world of forms.

The ultimate move in Greek-inspired thought, by Christians like Aquinas, was to tap into the biblical idea of God's not being containable even by the highest heavens, placing him outside the Greek-inspired idea of the cosmos. This tends to make God very distant (as in the mediaeval Ptolemaic universe in which God's heaven was the distant outermost celestial sphere), and it also poses the problem of how God might interact with his world, except through chains of intermediaries. But it is the concept most Christians have inherited, as they vehemently deny to their scientific friends that heaven is "up," without having any clear idea whatsoever of where it actually *is*. Even to say God is "outside" the universe is a problem, given the rather vague notion we must now have of the shape of our immense universe, which doesn't seem to *have* an outside.

Amongst the Greeks Aristotle, in particular, did excellent work on causation. His division of causes into four – the formal, material, efficient and final causes – is still important today, even in science. Werner Heisenberg (of Uncertainty Principle fame), for example, consciously drew on it for his understanding of quantum theory.

But I think for simplicity's sake here we can ignore the first two and consider only "efficient causation" (what modern science exclusively covers, ie how things happen) and "final causation," (why things happen, ie what they are *for*).

In Aristotle's thinking, all four causes always operate, even though he was at best unclear about the existence of God. To him, nature itself always works towards specific ends (that is, teleologically) via specific means (efficient causes). Theories of true teleology without God are still seriously proposed today, for example by the celebrated philosopher Thomas Nagel in *Mind and Cosmos*. But as others have pointed out to Nagel, teleology always leads one back to a first source of purpose, God as First Cause. This was the major development from Aristotle that was made by the great mediaeval philosopher, Thomas Aquinas.

Modern Science

Aristotle's division of every cause in four ways enabled thinkers like Francis Bacon to consider them separately. Aristotelian philosophy – and the all too fallible Aristotelian science – had dominated European intellectual life for three centuries. But what, thought Bacon, if we were to abandon formal and material causes altogether, and take God's final causation for granted? We could then investigate efficient causes on their own by experimentation, to the great benefit of mankind.

With respect to my theme of choice, chance and necessity, Bacon's new science did not deny God's right to act purposefully in providence. Indeed, much of the discussion of the Royal Society in its early days was about the extent to which special providence determines efficient causes in the world, and therefore queers the pitch for regular science, unless patterns could be discerned in providence itself. Their convenient conclusion (as Protestants highly suspicious of the miracles of Catholicism) was that divine providential choice was rare enough to be disregarded in practice. It is hard to know if they would have reached the same conclusion had they known of chaos theory or quantum mechanics, of which more later.

The other early-modern development that is important for our discussion is the emergence of the concept of "laws of nature." To Aristotle and Aquinas, how things behaved in nature was the result of their particular "substantial forms": all the individual things that are heavy possess a tendency to fall, and so on. It is easy to dismiss these ideas when they are linked to outdated mediaeval science, but it is a valid way to consider things. It has the disadvantage, though, that it is difficult to make generalisations across the whole range of natural phenomena from the character of the particular thing one is investigating.

But for Protestants rejecting the Catholic Aquinas, an alternative idea held great appeal – that of God's law. If God gave mankind a holy law through Moses, would he not previously have decreed laws for the rest of his creation? If those general laws can be discovered, one will be able to explain every particular instance of their effects within nature.

This is an appealing idea which has endured, and which underpins Monod's concept of scientific necessity and, indeed, the whole of modern science. But one can immediately appreciate that the idea of such laws is fundamentally religious, and indeed exclusively Judaeo-Christian. Even within that framework it presents intellectual problems, and it becomes very problematic indeed once God is removed from the picture (as I will argue in a later chapter).

The Enlightenment

This removal of God is what did, indeed, happen as all previous sources of authority were rejected in the Enlightenment, in favour of pure reason (as it was thought to exist – in fact, postmodernism has demonstrated that even reason withers once its religious roots are cut).

The principal religious movement of the Enlightenment was Deism. What this primarily discarded was the dogmas of the Bible, such as the deity of Christ, and any concept of special providence. What it retained was the idea of a supreme being outside the cosmos (channeling Aquinas) and his immutable laws of nature (channeling Bacon).

And so arose the familiar idea of an aloof clockmaker God winding up the watch of creation at the beginning of time, and watching it tick deterministically through every event of history. To a Deist

like Gottfried Leibniz, Isaac Newton's theistic suggestion that God might sometimes tinker with his timepiece was an affront to divine dignity:

Sir Isaac Newton and his followers have also a very odd opinion concerning the work of God. According to their doctrine, God Almighty wants to wind up his watch from time to time: otherwise it would cease to move. He had not, it seems, sufficient foresight to make it a perpetual motion.

That attitude exists up to the present day in discussions about divine action, as I have already mentioned. But even more to the point, a God who is entirely removed from the operation of the universe is also entirely irrelevant, and may as well be discarded altogether. You already have a universe which, according to your philosophy, operates entirely by "natural laws" (which now comes to mean "independent of God"). To the extent that you can develop your science then you will understand the world in its entirety. You will have a theory of everything. You will in fact be God. Is that not a familiar theme in our day?

Origins remain a problem for such a brand of atheism, but Epicurus comes to the rescue from the distant past: chance and necessity can never be disproved as the origin of all things. In fact, once Charles Darwin joins the party with a combination of chance and necessity which plausibly explains the mystery of life, even biology becomes a nail in God's coffin. Finally, adopting the idea of alternative universes from Science Fiction gives you the Multiverse. Speculative as it is (and decreasingly defensible as the fashionable String Theory has collapsed in the last decade), it allows you to bypass the problem of the alternatives of a true beginning in the Big Bang, or the infinite regression of an eternal universe, by placing the world's origins in some other evolving system that is beyond investigation or refutation.

The only problem is that, out in the real world, ordinary people still experience things which they can only explain by the providential choices of God. That primitive animism just won't go away.

5 Chance in Science

*All nature is but art, unknown to thee;
All chance, direction which thou canst not see.*

Alexander Pope

Why chance is not a fine thing

As I have mentioned, the proper meaning of “chance” or “random” within science is no more and no less than “of uncertain cause.” To the extent that events in science referred to as “random” or “chance” only reflect human ignorance, rather than the actual condition of the universe, they really belong under the label of “necessity,” or in my proposed theistic worldview, “fidelity.”

This is what physicists assume for the movement of individual molecules in a gas, for example: we are ignorant about them, but have no reason to believe they buck the laws of physics. In other words such events are governed by the same regular patterns that determine that things always fall downwards, that water always dissolves salt, and so on. In Christian terms such lawlike events may be seen as the way God ensures that we, and all his creatures, have a broadly reliable world in which to live, and so they are expressions of God’s faithfulness, however he achieves them. Hence my replacement term for Monod’s necessity, “fidelity.”

But if there are events in nature that are truly random, in the sense of “uncaused” or “undetermined,” then we have a profound theological problem. For creation doctrine, particularly when extended to the doctrine of providence (in some Christian traditions understood as *creation continua*, “continued creation”), teaches us that all things in heaven and earth were caused by God, the First Cause, and “*without him was not anything made that was made*” (John 1:3). It is logically impossible that God could cause an event, even indirectly, that is in fact uncaused, or that he could create causelessness.

Similarly, since God “*declares the end from the beginning*” (Isaiah 46:10), which is expressed in the classical philosophy of Aquinas as “God directing all things towards their proper ends,” then one would have to exempt the entire class of ontologically random events from his causation and determination. Chance would then be a wild card continually disrupting God’s wise rule of his creation.

If, alternatively, we take the more scientific definition of chance as “of unknown cause” (epistemological randomness) but expand it to mean that chance events are unknown to God as well as to man, then we must claim that the omniscient God does not know events that he himself created. And that is absurd. In effect, chance becomes a kind of Demiurge independent of God. Such dualism is not Christianity, but it is surprisingly common.

There is actually no reason to suppose that God should even want to have that kind of randomness in his creation. The very concept of creation matches the Greek idea of “cosmos,” or order, as opposed to “chaos.” The whole Genesis 1 account is about God’s bringing order and purpose to that which was “formless and void.” That some Christians are keen to assert that God did create ontological randomness is largely because they wrongly believe that science has, in fact, revealed such a category of events, which they dare not therefore deny.

Alternatively they confuse chance with “liberty,” to assert that nature is spontaneous and free rather than merely mechanically determined by a “puppet master” God. This, as I will show in a later chapter, is simply incoherent.

In fact, there are only three concepts in science which might give weight to the acceptance of “ontological randomness” in nature, and none stands up to scrutiny.

1 Statistical Science

In the 19th century, James Clerk Maxwell, a devout Christian, revolutionized science by developing statistical mechanics. The basic concept of this is that although the individual movements of small entities, such as molecules in a gas, cannot be known, yet one can calculate and hence predict the sum of their movements in statistical ways.

Up to that point the theoretical basis of science was that one should uncover the nature of individual causes and effects, to build up to the big picture. But knowing individual causes and effects for billions of individual molecules was a practical impossibility. This was the dilemma laid out by Pierre-Simon Laplace in 1814 and known as “Laplace’s Demon.” In theory, he said, an omniscient being able to measure the exact position and velocity of every atom in the universe could predict the whole future, given the (presumed) universality of the laws of nature. God would be such a being, of course, though Laplace is reputed to have told Napoleon “I have no need of that hypothesis.”

The real problem was, of course, that no such demon is on the phone to scientists, and no science could ever gather such a huge amount of information. You would need another whole universe to gather and store the information, though that conclusion from information theory was not known to Laplace. Maxwell, however, showed that this does not matter, because the statistical behavior of large numbers of components such as molecules would sufficiently explain the behaviour of the whole system.

Over time, popular understanding of Maxwell’s discovery has come to be that the interactions of the individual molecules are random. So they are, but only in the limited sense of being in practice unknowable. We can, in fact, study each individual molecule’s movement with the right instruments – but only Laplace’s Demon, or God himself, can know all of them. It is simply a question of limited resources, not of intrinsically unknowable things. Each molecule’s movements fully obey the laws of physics, and so may well actually be fully deterministic.

However, it is instructive to read how the church elder Maxwell introduced his statistical concept to his fellow-scientists:

Would it not be more profound and feasible to determine the general constraints within which the deity must act than to track each event the divine will enacts?

What he is saying (as a matter of Christian faith) is that all events are *not* “necessary,” but ordered individually by God’s divine and free will. Yet in aggregate they generate knowable statistical patterns. This precedence of choice over statistics is not mysterious, for it is true in behavioural science too. One can track and predict statistical patterns of human behavior in road usage or purchasing trends, yet the statistics are the result of a myriad individual choices.

This is an important point, for I have been told more than once by working scientists that “the causes of random events are governed by statistical laws.” That is to put the cart before the horse, as the simple example of tossing a coin will show.

Coin tosses are a poster-child for the power of statistical laws, which supposedly dictate that a “fair” coin will produce heads and tails at an equal rate, and increasingly so the more tosses are counted. The coin tosses *have* to produce that result, *ergo* they are subject to a law of chance.

The nonsense of this may be shown in practice, or here as a thought experiment, by conceiving a coin tossing machine. Imagine a machine that accurately applies just enough force to flick the edge of a pound coin up exactly 30 degrees. If it starts as heads, it will fall back and end up as heads 100% of the time. Now adjust your machine so it flicks the coin 95 degrees. It will reliably tip over and land on tails 100% of the time. Increase the power to deliver a 20cm rise and two and a half turns, and your now more realistic coin toss will still invariably end up as tails, totally ignoring the so-called statistical laws. Such machines have been built, and the coins always end up consistently as predicted by the mechanics of the machine..

What determines the statistics are the choices made in designing the system. A coin designed to be flat has only two possible outcomes when tossed (discounting the ultra-rarity of landing on its edge), whatever the angle at which it actually lands. For exactly half of the angles it will tip over, and for the other half it will tip back. 50% heads, 50% tails, exactly.

The individual outcomes are determined by how you choose to toss it and the deterministic laws of physics – only normally you can’t control your muscles accurately enough to be sure how hard you tossed it within quite broad limits. That lack of knowledge, and the reliability of the laws of physics, determine the statistical outcome. There is no ontological chance involved.

But note this – nothing in this system would preclude God from modulating your muscular effort, or even giving the coin a subtle shove, in order to determine the result of any individual coin toss:

The lot is cast into the lap, but its every decision is from the LORD. (Proverbs 16:33)

Perhaps in contradiction to Maxwell, there is no “must” about the way God determines such events. At best statistical science is always an approximation, because in the real world a million different factors affect outcomes. Experiments are designed to exclude as many of those extraneous factors as possible, but even in physics, let alone biology, points seldom match the theoretical graph exactly. God has plenty of room to order individual events *and* maintain the world in a sufficiently orderly way.

As a further illustration of the folly of making individual events the result of statistical laws, a serious writer attempting to show how probability discredits Christian belief says:

“How could the suicide of say, Goethe’s young Werther really be his own decision, if the suicide rates remained constant for decades on end?”

Perhaps more than the dice throw, the inverted logic here is striking. How, exactly, is that supposed to work? Is suicide imposed on people by a probability law, and attempts at prevention doomed since the statistical rate is a given? Any fool should see that the problem has been stated back to front: in fact, the complex true causes of suicide, culminating in a disordered choice, may in large populations be seen to result in some pattern. To treat self-evidently volitional people as if they were inert gas molecules demonstrates blind adherence to a pathetically weak metaphysical system.

In closing this section, let me highlight an important instance of statistical science, and that is the “random mutations” that are said to lie behind significant evolutionary changes, thus sparking the whole debate about evolution *versus* creation. Speaking scientifically, “random” here means simply that the exact causes of the mutation are unknown to us. More precisely in the jargon of evolutionary biology they are “random with respect to fitness,” which simply means that we don’t see an obvious link between the many variations seen and the ability of the organism to survive and reproduce.

But just as it might take only one particularly significant coin toss for God to determine some important human decision, having no obvious effect on the statistical pattern of tosses, so key stages of a sequence of mutations, all (like Maxwell’s individual events) determined by God’s providential choice, could assure the arrival of the exact changes planned by the Creator. Any randomness is entirely in the eye of the beholder, but choice is a reasonable inference from the end result of the beautifully functioning organism.

2 Chaos Theory

Chaos, in the scientific sense, is less mysterious than it first seems when we hear about butterfly wings causing hurricanes on the other side of the world. Some physical systems are quite predictable and stable: lob a squash ball at a flat wall and even a mediocre player will know roughly where it will end up. But bounce it off a small stone globe and even minor variations of lob will send the ball bouncing off every which way. This is because in such a system variations tend to be magnified, rather than dampened.

Or perhaps you’re clever enough to balance a large pebble on edge. You won’t be clever enough to predict which way it will fall if a sudden breeze destabilizes it. Yet the laws which govern its fall are exactly the same laws of gravity we have always known. The direction of fall is, in theory, deterministic – but we have insufficiently accurate information to predict it. It is another example of epistemological randomness.

This unpredictability has led many to speak of chaos as involving “randomness.” And some quite intelligent people, confused in their understanding of “chance,” will say that chaos theory shows the universe not to be under God’s control but random. For example, because the weather is a random system, they say, it is wrong to suggest that God controls the weather. But in fact chaos theory only shows that the universe, and the weather, are not under *our* control.

One classic example of chaos is the Three Body problem of gravity, which was known to Newton himself as he developed his gravitational laws. Consider two heavenly bodies orbiting each other in isolation, and their paths can be easily predicted by Newton’s laws. But add a third body, and the system’s movements become increasingly unpredictable, even to this day.

This is because the third body turns the system into a chaotic one, in which immeasurably small differences in initial conditions lead to dramatically different outcomes. If you could make measurements as accurately as God created the bodies and their orbits, you could predict exactly how things would work. But you can’t. Hence, although in the solar system the bodies are far enough apart to appear to have stable orbits, mathematical predictions about its distant future simply cannot be made.

That is what led Newton to suggest that God might, perhaps, have to make “mid-course corrections” to the planets from time to time, to keep the system stable. The philosopher Leibnitz laughed at such

an idea, as we have seen, and the story is still trotted out as evidence that Newton wavered in his scientific integrity by suggesting an essentially theistic idea of divine maintenance of the universe.

But in fact Newton was mathematically more correct than Leibniz, whose calculations showing the solar system to be stable made approximations in ignorance of what we now know about chaos theory. Even today the future of the solar system still cannot be calculated on scientific principles: it can only be simulated on super-computers programmed with past astronomical data, using marginally different variables within the possible range and large numbers of “runs.” Around 1% of these simulations show an eventual collision between planets of the inner solar system far in the future.

Newton was perhaps unduly pessimistic, then, but we should note that only human ignorance, not chance, is involved here. Only one of the many possible simulations is true *now*, and it will remain true by the laws of nature unless something else changes. We just cannot know which one it is, but there is no reason to assume it is within the 99% rather than the 1%. God knows.

Nevertheless the prevalence of chaotic systems, such as those involving fluid dynamics like the climate, destroys the old Deistic dream that the universe is like a giant clock whose every motion could, in theory, be known to science. Chaos guarantees that we cannot know the future, even if it were fully determined by laws of nature without any further action from God. Scripture, however, gives us no inkling that God has ever left the universe to get on with things on its own.

Indeed, chaos theory provides some hints about the loci where God *might* best act to bring about change without also causing disasters. A surprising number of natural systems – including the solar system – are best described as being “on the edge of chaos.” Mostly they are fairly stable, but they are close enough to instability to be significantly altered relatively easily. It is this fact that enables our own ability to make significant alterations to many things in the world. And it is this fact that could make the direction of the world’s historical events a matter of God’s applying minimal force in the right place, rather than wrestling against immovable objects of nature with irresistible force.

An analogy might be the difference between a stable transport plane and a fighter jet. The first is designed for stability and will almost fly itself. But changing direction is hard work and slow. However, the latter is designed to operate on the edge of instability, making it more difficult to fly, but massively more manoeuvrable. Near-chaotic systems are the most obvious place for the exercise of divine choice, in contrast to the stable systems that manifest his fidelity towards his creatures.

3 Quantum Events

Quantum events are the only category of events in nature which one can truly say are not determined by local conditions. And so it is common for Epicureans to say that they are indeed an example of uncaused events (which accounts for the theory of the quantum vacuum leading to the formation of the universe, mentioned in an earlier chapter).

The weirdness of quantum theory is sufficiently well known to spare both you and me from dwelling on it. But some simple observations suggest that, for all our remaining ignorance, the idea that quantum events manifest ontological chance will not run.

You’ll probably be aware of the phenomenon of radioactive decay, which is a quantum process. Unstable radioactive atomic nuclei decay into more stable elements. It is such individual atomic events that are registered on a Geiger counter. There is no way to predict when any individual nucleus will undergo this quantum change. But in a given sample of a particular element, the decay will be

exponential, with a half-life that is so predictable that it forms the basis for radioactive dating of various types.

So although there is no apparent cause, even in theory, within the physical universe for each individual quantum event, the radioactive atoms seem to be aware that they are contributing to a predictable statistical pattern in which they have a particular part to play, a pattern that is different for each element.

That gives us no idea of how the game works, but it does tell us that the game has rules, and that the individual atoms obey them, or else one would expect to see completely unpredictable rates of radioactive decay. Now, it might be that viewing half-life as the rule which atoms obey is as back-to-front as saying that coin-tosses are governed by statistical rules. But the bottom line is that somehow radioactive decay – and therefore in all likelihood every quantum event – is orderly.

Werner Heisenberg accounted for quantum indeterminacy by the interactions of particles with the entire world, even in a controlled experiment. If he is correct, quantum events would be examples, like chaos or statistical science, of the practical impossibility of knowing enough about the system to predict it. No experiment can control for the whole world.

One or two thinkers, notably professor of theology and science Robert John Russell, have used the concept of quantum indeterminacy to “make room” for divine action without incurring the charge that God is “interfering with nature.” Notice that distaste for God’s acting within the natural world depends on seeing the universe in a deistic way, as being governed entirely by the laws of nature which, having created, God would be wrong to break. We have already seen that there are alternative ways of looking at things, and I will explore this further a bit later on.

But Russell’s argument runs along the lines that, since there seem to be no physical laws governing quantum events, God could “legitimately” determine them individually sometimes, or often, and hence play a role in managing the course of world events.

The big problem with this, apart from the questionable idea of God using a scientific get-out clause to circumvent his own laws, is that there is every indication that, with a few exceptions, quantum strangeness at the molecular level has no impact whatsoever on the macroscopic world. It is a case where the totality of quantum events is simply the predictable behavior of the world, understood as a statistical sum.

There are exceptions to this gulf between the quantum world and our world. Human physics experiments are one, as is quantum computing if it becomes practical. More surprising, it appears that some animals may use quantum events for sophisticated functions like navigation in bird migrations.

It has been suggested that biological mutations might be triggered by, say, the effect of single photons on genetic material, and this would be a macro-effect of quantum physics. Evidence for this seems lacking. It seems to arise from Hermann Muller’s theory that since hard radiation causes grotesque mutations (in fruit flies, for example), then evolution could proceed from micro-mutations caused by far lower doses. In fact he was wrong – there is a threshold for radiation-induced mutations, and it lies far above the quantum level.

More exotic, but equally undiscovered, might be that something in the DNA chemistry of living things utilizes some kind of quantum physics to induce useful mutations. After all, the brains of homing-pigeons must have got the idea from somewhere.

But if such a phenomenon were ever found, then like Russell's "quantum creation" proposal, it would only show that teleology, natural in this case, and not randomness, underlies any significant effect of quantum events in the large-scale world. In this case cells would be, somehow, directing their own evolution using quantum events. Self-directed evolution is an idea increasingly common at the fringes of evolutionary theory, as in the work of James Shapiro, so it might not be impossible. But neither would it be due to chance.

And so we see that ontological randomness really has no place in any of these three areas of statistical science, chaos theory and quantum physics, at least as they could affect the reality that matters to us. And if ontological randomness does not exist here, then there is really nowhere else in the universe, of which we have knowledge, in which it could have a place. So even before we come to an acceptance of God, and his active choice in the direction the world takes, there really is precious little evidence that its alternative chance, in the absolute, ontological sense, exists at all.

Epistemological chance – which is only another way of describing human uncertainty – certainly exists aplenty. But there is nothing particularly profound in saying that there is a lot we don't know. This kind of chance was, before modern science, the only kind known to mediaeval philosophers like Aquinas.

And so, Aquinas said, we legitimately use the word "chance" to describe things whose causes we can't understand. The orbit of an asteroid may have been determined by the laws of physics when the solar system began, and hence that it was always destined to encounter the earth at a certain location on a certain day. But to the inhabitant of Kamchatka in Russia in 2013, when a fireball exploded overhead and the windows of his flat shattered, its arrival was a chance event. Chance can therefore only be considered with reference to particular minds lacking particular knowledge – it is never absolute.

Aquinas gives the example of two servants meeting by chance in a market, neither realizing that their master's instructions to each individually had determined that outcome in advance, quite deliberately. Epistemological chance, then, is by no means outside the providence of God. Indeed, for the Christian, the habit of substituting "providence" for "chance" (or coincidence, or even the dreadful term "Godincidence") in our daily conversation is theologically healthy.

And here's a thing – it doesn't damage our scientific thinking in any way to consider mutations as "providential" rather than "random," although our secular friends will doubtless feel it displays too much metaphysical commitment. That would be a legitimate complaint if "random" were customarily understood to mean, as it should, simply "unknown." But Monod's book shows us that it is usually used by biologists bundled with a scientifically illegitimate metaphysical commitment to materialism, or else Monod's book would surely have been entitled *Ignorance and Necessity*.

6 Necessity in Science

*Look for the bare necessities
The simple bare necessities
Forget about your worries and your strife
I mean the bare necessities
Old Mother Nature's recipes
That brings the bare necessities of life*

Terry Gilkyson

Necessity is just regularity

The eighteenth century philosopher David Hume is famous for his argument that the link between what we call “causes” and their “effects” is not one of necessity. All we can really say for certain, he wrote, is that when A happens (such as applying a hammer to a window) B has always, in our experience, subsequently happened (it broke).

The whole question may seem to be one of those “how many angels on the head of a pin” distractions from things that actually matter, and as one would expect other philosophers have weighed in over the centuries to dispute his argument (and the number of angels involved). But if nothing else it reminds us that it is only the regularity of sequences of events that enables us to investigate causes at all, and also that there is more than one way to explain why particular effects follow particular causes.

On the first point, it follows that explanatory science can only be performed on phenomena that can regularly be observed or experimentally caused. A careful scientist might accurately *report* a unique event, such as an elephant giving birth to a human child or, less fantastically, Jesus’s turning of water into wine at Cana. But there could be no *scientific* explanation in the absence of such events recurring, though that would make them no less true.

If they did recur, the first job of “science” would be to record a pattern, such as “elephants have occasionally been reliably recorded as giving birth to humans” or “This man Jesus turns water into wine at will.” The next stage would be to work out that some kind of *necessity* governed those patterns, rather than “chance.” Only then could scientific explanations be sought. Perhaps human births from elephants occur only at total solar eclipses above particular altitudes after certain bestial human rituals. Perhaps Jesus is not an ordinary man (further investigation is required).

It is interesting that when actual events are truly anomalous, with respect to what is commonly experienced, they tend to be either denied or ignored, sometimes passionately. As a London medical student I once saw a hovercraft waiting at the traffic lights in Vauxhall Bridge Road, and when I arrived at the hospital hastened to ask my fellow students to assure me I wasn’t dreaming. Since then, having failed to find any reference to such an event, even in the internet age, it is exceedingly difficult not to revert to the belief that it must have been a dream.

As a more scientific example, NASA scientists will treat the scantiest data as evidence that life may exist on Mars, or on some distant exo-planet. But most will not even *have* a theory about the welter of “official” sightings of UFOs recently, apparently applying a completely different paradigm about the likelihood of extra-terrestrial life: on exo-planets alien life is likely, but around naval exercises it is not. Why would that be?

Applying this last example to my second point about Hume – that any causal chain may have alternative explanations – we may observe that those scientists who *do* suggest an explanation for UFOs other than fraud, tricks of the light and so on, are likely to go for that of interplanetary alien vehicles. But given how little we know about the phenomena, they might equally be angels, devils or the interstellar equivalent of dolphins, operating under some exotic physics, cavorting in our atmosphere for fun. The explanation would seem to be that, aeroplanes being a regular phenomenon, the anomaly is squeezed into the closest available mould. The default explanation in mediaeval times would probably have been spiritual beings. And so given human psychology, not only might highly unusual acts of God be explained away as something else: they might not even be registered as phenomena at all.

To return to the bigger picture, even routine events in the world have many possible “global” explanations. It could be that, following Aristotle, the “form” of entities governs what will happen when they interact with other forms. Under that model hydrogen has within its nature, when it encounters the form of oxygen, a propensity to make an entirely new form called water. Rather mysterious.

Or perhaps (adapting Hume) God undertakes to create water whenever hydrogen and oxygen happen to meet in the world, a once-popular and still viable idea called “occasionalism.” That too is rather mysterious – but perhaps no more so than Aristotle’s unexplained forms.

In fact the preferred option of scientists is to explain such things in terms of universal laws – in this case the laws of chemistry. The reactive gases hydrogen and oxygen interact to form a molecule we call “water,” which for not very obvious reasons hidden within these laws, has unpredictable properties entirely different from either element. That explains it! But it doesn’t, really – it is another rather mysterious idea which we happen to have got used to since Bacon’s time, and which we have worked through in rather more detail than the other approaches. That makes it more plausible to us, and it is certainly useful, but it is not necessarily the way things are.

There might be yet other ways to account for things, which include combinations of concepts. For example, the classical Christian doctrine of *concurrence* holds that God maintains all causes – not just all *things* – in being. Occasionalism may not be his way of acting, but he might be actively maintaining either the natures of things (forms) or their habitual interactions (laws) in being. And that thoroughly orthodox doctrine of providence is no less hands-on than occasionalism, for both occasionalism and concurrence describe God’s fidelity in governing his world.

But however things are organized in the universe, as limited human beings we cannot actually determine that anything in nature is “necessary.” We can only observe that it is regular.

Laws of nature

Let us consider those “laws of nature” for a moment. To a Tudor Christian like Francis Bacon, comparing the patterns in nature to the laws of Moses was natural and desirable. Partly that was due to the intellectual influence of the Bible, but partly it was because the despised Aristotelian philosophy of Aquinas inevitably populated the universe with an infinite number of purposeful “forms,” each with its own goals, albeit under the providence of God. That seemed, perhaps, a little idolatrous.

Divinely appointed law could therefore be seen as the single, divine, principle imposed upon a purely inert matter, thus “disenchanted” the creation and recognising God as the sole spiritual power. This

was particularly the case since atomism, originally proposed by our Greek friend Democritus, became popular through early modern thinkers like René Descartes and, in England, Robert Boyle. Early modern science was convinced by the idea that all matter was composed of tiny, inert corpuscles, whose collisions (governed by God's laws) would account for all events.

Incidentally that is why Isaac Newton's concept of gravity later encountered strong scientific opposition. Because it suggested "spooky action at a distance" it seemed to undermine the whole way the universe was thought to work. Eventually a fudge was achieved by inventing the idea of "fields," which could, without being explicable, act at a distance and not, for unclear reasons, be spooky.

The attractive idea of universal laws begins to cause problems once one asks what these laws actually are, where they are, and how they act. The Law of Moses was revealed to the prophet, written down and stored in the Tabernacle (especially the Decalogue on tablets of stone in the Ark of the Covenant). As it was copied and taught, it also existed in the minds of men, who *chose* to obey its ordinances if they were obedient. The whole process is quite transparent.

We know, however, that much of the time they were not obedient. Examining the behavior of the Israelites at any stage of history would not enable you to derive the Law of Moses, though archaeologists do identify Israelite sites from the lack of pork bones and relative paucity of idols.

The supposed laws of nature, however, are deduced *entirely* from observations of natural entities, on the assumption that inert matter must obey them of necessity. But *where* exactly are these laws? And *what* are they? They are represented by mathematical symbols, but no equation on a blackboard ever moved anything. In any case, most valid mathematical equations are not represented in laws of nature. What makes *these* particular equations so powerful?

In a theistic universe, one can suggest that the laws exist in the mind of God. But in that case, one might as well say that God simply causes things to happen on a regular basis by his direct actions, through occasionalism or concurrence, which is the "primitive animistic" idea taught in the Bible. I would suggest that it is not a bad idea, since the equations would still apply.

There is even more of a problem, though, when one wishes to remove the mind of God from the picture. Somehow the atheist agrees there are laws which apply to everything in the universe, in all places at all times, and yet they are entirely invisible and intangible, and there was no lawgiver. The Decalogue, it seems, exists without Moses, and without any stone tablets. The laws would seem to be as mystical and spiritual as God himself – only under a materialistic worldview that is not possible.

In the light of that difficulty, the fact that laws are purposeless apart from God, and therefore completely unexplained, is a relatively minor matter. Remember that the Baconian scientists, by focusing on "efficient causes" alone, could avoid speculating on *why* God puts those causes into action. The further step to atheism denies that there even is a "why." In theory, that leads to a world in which nothing has a purpose. Or, as the New Atheists used to delight in claiming, "We must make our own purpose."

In practice, it means that scientists usually act as if purpose *does* exist, and then backtrack to preserve their worldview. There are very few papers on evolution that manage to avoid saying things like "This feature evolved in order to..." David Attenborough made a career out of treating evolution as a problem-solving tool, employed by fish wanting to take to land for example, even though

undirectedness is the keystone of Darwinian evolution. Richard Dawkins famously said that "Biology is the study of complicated things that give the appearance of having been designed for a purpose." The doctor who taught me haematology at medical school was always saying, "Of course, we should not speak teleologically"... and then she invariably gave a long teleological explanation of the body's wonderful mechanisms.

This inability to explain anything much in nature without invoking purpose may be because of the same limitation of goal-orientated human nature that made us invent gods, working out their purposes, in primitive times. Or it may rather be because things that give every appearance of having a purpose actually do.

7 Chance, Necessity and Impossibility

*Yesterday, upon the stair,
I met a man who wasn't there!
He wasn't there again today,
Oh how I wish he'd go away!*

William Hughes Mearns

Proving the ordinary impossible

In the previous chapter I briefly touched on the observation that many scientists respond to what one might call the “occasional” phenomenon of UFOs simply by ignoring them as a phenomenon, whilst others will categorise them into the least irregular category available.

There is an internal psychological logic to this, in that singular events that do not fit known patterns predispose one to disbelief – like the proverbial case of the first person to see a black swan being disbelieved, when it was well known that all swans are white. And since known categories are familiar, if one does believe the phenomenon it makes some sense to categorise it with what is most common (an alien kind of human flying machine) rather than with some new category (an interplanetary dolphin or an interstellar swan). Rationally speaking, though, both trying to classify something totally novel, and discounting it entirely, are psychological responses rather than scientific ones.

After all, when your scientists are already wondering how to perform travel to other stars, there is no valid scientific reason to deny that there may be others returning the compliment. But because we have not achieved the first, and have no certain knowledge of the second, the other possibilities (including angels) should still be on the table. “But angels don’t exist!” And aliens do?

Psychological responses are one thing. Materialism, however, is notorious for rendering logically impossible even things that are not anomalies, but normalities. One of these is choice itself, and so in a book prioritizing choice and purpose in the universe, it will be worth examining the materialist arguments against them.

Three years ago I was discussing the question of free-will with an evolutionary biologist who is also an atheist materialist. He said that if human decisions are caused (necessity), as is argued in the philosophical position called “compatibilism,” then they appear to be deterministic and not free. If, on the other hand, they are spontaneous and uncaused, they are not decisions but random events. Either way, rational choices are an illusion, because of

...the fundamental incoherence of free will, that in order to be free it must be both uncaused and non-random.

You see the problem? He agreed with me that truly random choices, if they existed at all, would be arbitrary in the sense of totally mad. The only alternative is compatibilist choices, which would actually be the result of efficient causes in our brains, in a deterministic chain presumably stretching back to the Big Bang. And since there *is* nothing but chance and necessary, efficient, causation, free will is at best an epiphenomenon or, worse, an illusion.

The same argument applies to God as to mankind. And so, to quote Douglas Adams explain the Babel Fish in *The Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy*,

"Oh dear," says God. I hadn't thought of that," and promptly vanishes in a puff of logic.

It takes a good deal of *chutzpah* to deny the experience of every human being in every time and place every minute of every day, in favour of an "illusion" (but an illusion of what, exactly? It would have to be the illusion of the core experience of our lives). But the argument often doesn't stop there. The same materialist debunking argument has been applied to consciousness itself. Often Descartes gets the blame for why this argument has any traction, probably with some justification. His reasoning led him to the familiar concept of an immaterial rational soul riding in our bodies like a driver in a car. The external world – including our bodies themselves – thereby became merely passive material objects governed by whatever laws of nature were waiting to be discovered. How the immaterial soul controlled the physical body was the "mind-body problem" that has proved intractable for this "Cartesian dualism" for four hundred years.

Slowly, after Descartes, the physical sciences became applied to biology as well as to the inorganic world, then to neurology. Meanwhile the Enlightenment gradually abolished God, and hence together with him the plausibility of Descartes' immaterial souls. Accordingly, by similar kinds of argument to those employed against free will, consciousness too came to be categorized as an illusion. But an illusion fooling whom?

The conclusion truly is bizarre, because not only is consciousness the *only* thing we know for certain ("*Cogito, ergo sum*," as Descartes began his argument), but it is the sole means by which we know anything else whatsoever. If it is an illusion, then so much more is the science and logic that, supposedly, disprove it. Enlightenment "pure reason" turns out to abolish itself by its own chance and necessity. Somehow, however, the reductive materialists who abolish consciousness in this way insist on the reliability of science as the only source of true knowledge. But why listen to them if their minds and ideas are illusory?

Making the Ordinary Crucial

There is, of course, an alternative – and that is to reject the premise that efficient material causes are all that there is, which means also to deny that chance and necessity are the only causes. But that inevitably entails that mind itself, together with its will and purpose, is not a *result* of causes at all, but is a cause in its own right.

And not only is it *a* cause, but a primary cause, and a necessarily immaterial one since it cannot (as the materialists have so generously proven) be the result of material causes. And so although I have been arguing in this book, essentially, that "chance and necessity" are alternative metaphysical *choices* to "choice and fidelity," yet strict materialism itself saws off the branch on which it is sitting by asking us to believe the impossible, that is that we do not exist except as illusions.

Now, to identify mind and will as primary causes is not necessarily to claim that they are uncaused, still less that they are the First Cause. But they are caused by mind, not by matter, the subjective giving rise to the subjective. Having accepted that these fundamentally subjective entities are also immaterial, and therefore not amenable to scientific investigation, we may still accept that they have been created by God, analogously at least in imitation of his own subjectivity.

Furthermore we need not deny that, although physically uncaused, they may well be influenced by themselves, or by other minds and by events they perceive – and even by God himself. And that is simply confirmed by our experience. To choose is to deliberate between options we consider with our minds, or feel with our bodies. Our choices are not random, but they are freely made in the light of alternatives. This is even so when our own biases towards sin or addictions render that freedom only partial. They are not uncaused, but self-caused by the subjective “I.”

Now consider where this has led us. Our choices exist (but you knew that already!), and cannot have been caused by chance or necessity. And I have already spent many pages arguing that the existence of chance and necessity are themselves doubtful, being better explained by the regular and contingent choices of God acting upon the world.

That would appear to make minds, and the choices pursued by minds, far from illusory or epiphenomenal, but rather of primary importance to everything that happens. Purpose is everywhere you look. If you remove minds and choice from the universe, what do you have left? That’s a fascinating question on which I will speculate in the final chapter.

8 Choice, God and Science

*Lord God, from whom all life
And all true gladness springs,
Whose love and care shine everywhere
Among earth's common things;
Be present while we lift
Our song to thee, and pay
Heart-gratitude for all things good
About our path to-day.*

E. A. Burroughs

Miracle-free nature...

The aim of this book, I remind you, is not to convince materialists that an active God exists, but to get Christians to think coherently about how the God they worship is involved in creation. Many people, whose views I am trying to change, will have no argument with the *existence* of genuine choice, both divine and human, but they may hold this belief alongside those of chance and necessity.

One particular example is the Christian science writer Denis Alexander, who seeks to maintain a conventional scientific view of nature as independent of God, though maintained in existence by him as “general providence” (a Christian view termed “bare conservatism” by philosopher Freddie Freddoso to distinguish it from the occasionalism and concurrentism I have described before).

His argument is that God’s “special providence” towards human beings, for example in answering prayers, is for all intents and purposes just another word for “miracles,” which are also worked by God for the benefit of human beings.

But because both these types of unmediated divine action are exclusively works of grace towards *people*, he goes on to assert that we should look neither for miracles nor special providence in the world of nature, which is not subject to the kind of gracious care offered to humans by God. Nature, then, is entirely governed by natural laws in the best Deist tradition. I am unsure where Alexander stands on the question of chance, though to his credit he appears actually to use it in the strict scientific (that is, epistemological) sense.

...or a world suffused with providence

There is a big problem with this simplifying scheme, which is actually the same problem inherent in the conclusion of the early Royal Society members that special providence is rare enough to be disregarded when doing science. It is not just that it is rather presumptuous to suggest that God does not act in the way he calls “miraculous” in the care of the beasts or plants or even planets. The Scriptural witness is, after all, that he acts providentially and individually in the case of every sparrow that falls to the ground, and more widely in his provision of prey for the young lions, eagles, giving and taking life and so on. The teaching is notable in Psalm 104, but is also in a variety of other scattered texts. I am tempted to echo the habitual challenge of a preacher I knew: “Who *told* you that God only acts providentially towards humans?”

Alexander has, I suppose, to interpret all such passages in Scripture metaphorically. But that should in fairness commit him to the same policy for passages dealing with special providence towards humans, thereby ending up with frank Deism, a position he would vehemently disclaim. He does not deny special providence in fact, though he subsumes it to “miracle” in name.

The real problem is quite simply that, for all the theoretical methodology of science that is intended to remove the influence of people from natural cause and effect, the world is full of people interacting with the whole realm of nature in order even to exist. People affect nature, and without any doubt nature affects people. Therefore if there are 7.6 billion people towards whom God currently exhibits special providence – “miracle” if we insist on Denis Alexander’s unnuanced categories against two millennia of theological reflection – then there are also 7.6 billion niches within nature where that providence is “interfering” with nature’s supposed efforts to get on with its business uninterrupted.

Does God never answer prayer through natural causes? If not, he can scarcely answer prayer at all, because man and nature are what constitute the entire physical world. Even if God’s answers come through the direct actions of other people, their bodies still obey the laws of nature which, according to Alexander, should be operating autonomously, not under God’s controlling hand. A law with so many exceptions is not a law at all.

Let me exemplify this by referring to the writing of my privately printed book about a fire that destroyed our old chapel in 2009. As I interviewed the many people affected by it, what came across most strongly were the multiple experiences of special providence that my interviewees reported both in relation to their own lives, and to the circumstances of the fire and its aftermath.

The church member who found himself as Project Manager for the rebuild, and so was deeply involved at every stage, was nevertheless amazed when he read the book to find just how God had been “working behind his back” in the lives of and experiences of many others, and so indirectly affecting his own experience. That was quite apart from his own sense of God’s direct provision to him.

Researching that book, I heard how even the fire chief who attended the incident considered that heavy snow, which began to fall soon after the flames took hold, had “by a miracle” prevented what might have been a major local disaster, quenching the firebrands that might otherwise have set light to the many quaint thatched cottages in the village neighbourhood. The loss adjuster who lost his way and got trapped in the snow naturally looked favourably towards the church’s claim when we managed to engineer his rescue.

The fire itself, ridding the fellowship of an antiquated money-pit of a building that it had found no way of working round, proved an immense benefit both to us and our community as we rebuilt closer to the village centre. Paradoxically the snow that saved the rest of the village also assured the destruction of the chapel itself by delaying the fire team’s arrival, as well as buttering up the insurance man. And so on. Most of these providences were only “encouraging” or “faith-building” because they gave all the appearance that the actual circumstances were under God’s control. That is, God was influencing all the things in the natural world in which every one of those circumstances arose.

Now, a major incident like a fire, and especially a book of Christian recollections about a fire, concentrates the mind on providences. But whether people appreciate “special providence,” or ungratefully assume it is “coincidence,” the very principle that Denis Alexander rightly sets out about God’s abundant love and care for people indicates that such providence is, actually, ubiquitous. And

in that case it necessarily affects vast swathes of nature, wherever people or their interests are involved.

If God ever affects the weather providentially, for example, then the whole atmosphere gets in on the act – that after all was the implication of the hurricane caused by the butterfly flapping its wings on the other side of the world in the famous chaos theory example. If someone is supernaturally healed, it is real natural bacteria or cancer cells that lose their livelihood. If George Müller providentially finds a coin to feed his orphans in the street, then somebody else providentially got an actual hole in their physical pocket.

It should not really be controversial that the world cannot, in reality, be compartmentalised into “human” and “natural,” and Scripture gives no indication that God makes such a distinction. In Genesis 1 we are described simply as the latest product of the days of creation. It may occasionally be useful, as I will later on in the chapter on *Chance and Freedom*, to insist on a distinction such as that between humans who have actual free will, and irrational nature, which does not. But that does not apply here: one can no more sideline human affairs from nature than one can ignore the welfare of the people living in a national park to preserve it unspoiled. God created mankind to rule and tend the natural creation from within, according to Genesis 1. We are not, as some conservationists claim, interlopers on the scene, even interlopers providentially supported by God on our way to heaven. In other words, it doesn't seem possible to find many real places on earth where nature *doesn't* involve humans.

The exception, I suppose, would be where scientists have designed carefully controlled experiments specifically to exclude human (and therefore, in Denis Alexander's scheme, divine) influence. The problem with that is that since the entire experimental setup of such systems is human, it is the very worst example you could devise to prove the point.

Thomas Aquinas argued rigorously for the universality of divine providence throughout creation. I suggest that he made a better case than Denis Alexander has in this instance.

9 Natural and Supernatural

S'blood, there is something in this more than natural, if philosophy could find it out.
William Shakespeare

The elusive natural

This may be a good place to examine more closely the largely artificial dichotomy between the “natural” and the “supernatural,” a distinction whose proper understanding goes to the heart of the purpose of this book.

In recent years archaeologists have been excavating a possible site for the biblical Sodom and Gomorrah around Tall el-Hammam in the Jordan alluvial disk, and they have presented evidence for an asteroid air-burst that could explain its destruction around 1700 BC. Once again, I’m not concerned here about the truth of the claim itself. A space science journalist for *Physorg*, though, was convinced enough to write an article in 2018, drawing some naturalistic conclusions:

Now that it seems reasonable that a meteor airburst did destroy the area that may have contained Sodom, we can lay to rest the idea that the Christian God sent down fireballs to punish homosexuality. It looks like once again, it was a perfectly natural event that led to an apocalyptic, mythological story, and that what people once attributed to Gods and Goddesses is just nature.

I want to ask the writer what he thinks he means by the word “natural.” Usually in such discussions the only reply is to contrast it with “supernatural,” amplified by the term “miracle.” What is never spelled out, because it is not *thought* out, is that the usage of “natural” is closely related to that quasi-religious personified idea of “Nature,” which includes the idea that it is an entity entirely independent of God. At best that is a deistic concept, for as we have seen, as far as the Bible is concerned God is always intimately involved in nature, and indeed his is the will that keeps each part of it going moment by moment.

In their original etymology the words “nature” and “natural” refer simply to how a particular thing has been created, what it is like “by birth.” Therefore God is supernatural, because he was not created. But that is not what is in the modern mind that divorces the “natural” from the “supernatural,” because somehow the idea is that God is not, in a particular situation, involved. But to the orthodox Christian he *is*, and *must be*, involved in everything that happens. Yet to most people now, not really comprehending the orthodox teaching, if God *does* get involved, then it must be by a special miracle, to distinguish it from what is “natural.”

But that is a sub-biblical, “semi-deistic” idea of God’s activity. To be sure, in the Bible, and no doubt in the present day, God does miracles. But the distinctive thing about miracles is their obviously extraordinary character and their purpose as signs to mankind. In many cases the miracles isn’t even in the means, but in the timing. The creation of the world was not a miracle – it was... creation. And God’s daily general providence in the supply of all his creatures’ needs is not miraculous, but governmental. And even his special providence, for example in his answering of believer’s regular prayers for their daily bread, is not (*contra* Denis Alexander) miraculous, but providential.

At the same time, as C. S. Lewis points out in *Studies in Words*, the modern meaning of “supernatural” is mostly based on no clear concept at all, but on an emotional impression that something is, in his words, “uncanny, mysterious, odd, ‘rum.’” Yet God’s creation, and his daily provision, are not in the least “rum,” but are the daily bread-and-butter of our very existence. If we are to thank God for all things, it must be because all things come from his hand; even ordinary things. What is “natural” about that?

If we grant that, by some process – by *any* process – God’s creative work is still involved in the remarkable changes that have occurred to species over time, then “miraculous” is not the word to use – but neither perhaps is “natural,” if it implies that creative things happen all by themselves. The same is true of destructive events like the air-burst at Tall el-Hammam or the destructive *and* creative KT-event that destroyed the dinosaurs but opened the way for the diversification of birds and mammals.

Nature defined clearly

Does that mean, then, that the word “natural” has no meaning at all, and should be abandoned? I don’t think so, but we should always use it carefully, in a way that does not deny God’s involvement in creation or that is self-referential, or we will end up believing in the materialist account of the world.

In previous chapters I have tried to show that “ontological chance” has no real place in science. At levels above the quantum, at the very least, “chance” events are actually at root either manifestations of regular laws, whose exact workings are hidden from us; or they are perhaps, at least in some cases, the direct acts of God, equally unknown to us. In other words, to the extent that events are irregular, or “contingent,” we simply cannot know whence they arise. Remember that scientifically, that gap in our knowledge is what *makes* events random.

There is, on the other hand, a broad category of events which fit the regular patterns which we either experience day by day, or which are measured by scientific endeavour. Bearing in mind the previous discussion demonstrating that all we certainly know about such events is their predictability, and not their origin, then their single defining feature is their *regularity*. It is only because they are regular that we can describe them by mathematical equations called laws.

And along these lines Asa Gray, the Christian friend of Charles Darwin who first argued for God’s design within evolution by natural selection, concluded that what “natural” actually means is simply what is regularly seen in nature. No more and no less. He quotes Bishop Joseph Butler approvingly:

“The only distinct meaning of the word ‘natural’ is stated, fixed or settled; since what is natural as much requires and presupposes an intelligent mind to render it so, i.e., to effect it continually or at stated times, as what is supernatural or miraculous does to effect it for once.”

So our use of “natural” and “supernatural” changes subtly, but very significantly.

By “natural,” we consistently mean those things in creation which are regular, predictable and lawlike. That, of course, would include the statistical regularities which James Clerk Maxwell formulated, the overall trends in mutations which are dealt with by population genetics, radioactive half-lives governed by “random” quantum events, and so on.

We do *not* mean by “natural” contingent or anomalous events, whose mechanisms we cannot explain for the very reason of their irregularity. We call these “random,” which does not preclude the possibility that we might someday find natural processes to explain them. Lack of knowledge may often be remedied. But the word “random” must include all individual events we have not actually measured: we simply cannot pronounce that an unobserved molecular movement, a chaotic event or single quantum jump are “natural,” because we do not *know* they have followed some predictable course.

Neither do we mean by “natural” that God is not intimately involved in producing these events. According to orthodox doctrine he is. But the word “natural” is, under this definition, a neutral term that has a common meaning both for believers and unbelievers. It is purely empirical: if an occurrence is regular and repeatable, it is natural. If it is not repeatable, it is not natural. But it is not thereby assumed to be supernatural, in the sense of miraculous, either.

Appliance to science

Now let us see how that concept fits into the theological framework we’re developing. Unlike the materialists, Christians do not believe that regular and repeatable events in the world are produced by a fundamental *necessity*, but by the faithful government – the fidelity – of God, however he may achieve that in practice through laws, forms or direct action. And so a single causal concept is covered by several words: regularity, repeatability, lawlikeness and naturalness are all theologically neutral words that may be used equally by anybody. But for the believer, a word like “fidelity” reminds us that these terms contain a rich theological content about God and his world.

As for irregular events, the proper scientific term is “random,” signifying *always* that we do not have certain knowledge of their cause, and *never* that they have no cause. If we do not know their cause, because they are irregular and unpredictable, then we have no business calling them “natural,” since that would imply that they are not irregular but regular, and not of unknown but known cause.

This does not imply that everything we don’t know must be attributed to extraordinary actions of God. It is simply a recognition that what we don’t know, we can’t pretend to explain by science. That humble acceptance of uncertainty is an attitude that has become pretty uncommon in modern science, since the myth has been encouraged to develop that science must explain everything, or be esteemed a failure.

The Christian has no more knowledge of the precise causes of random events than the Epicurean does. Theologically, though, we know that God’s active will is behind every event. It is no skin off our nose if scientific investigation shows that some category of events deemed “random” subsequently turns out to be lawlike and, in Bishop Butler’s parlance, “natural.” Indeed, the inquisitive Christian scientist will be working hard to bring more of the world into what is understood. Yet God does not need to retreat into the gaps of the unknown, because even that which is well known is his work. Once one attributes every event to God, whether regular or contingent, the “God of the Gaps” accusation is simply meaningless. It is simply not true that science has progressively decreased the number of things we can attribute to God: it has simply increased the number we can regard as regularities.

What about the “Sodom event”? The skeptical writer actually has no idea whatsoever whether the putative asteroid was following a regular (aka natural) orbit, or not. Airbursts are not unknown, but

lethal airbursts over populous areas are, literally, unknown. No humans in history are known to have been killed by meteors or asteroids, apart from what is claimed for Sodom in 1700BC, though there are rumours of a few tribesmen killed by the Siberian Tunguska asteroid of 1908, and a woman was injured by one in Alabama in the 1950s. It was scarcely a regular event, “stated, fixed and settled.” However it occurred, though, God predicted it, and was its first cause.

Mark this, though. There could be many instances where God does choose to act “creatively” in an irregular way within creation, whether that be in ensuring that certain advantageous mutations occur within a species that eventually result in a new body-type, or in arranging some accidental circumstance that providentially saves the life of a believer, or in working a notable miracle. Although the scientist, as a scientist, would be correct to call such events “random,” since he can’t attribute the cause to a known regular process, what would really be happening is that God’s active governance of the world would be hidden in plain sight.

Yet that would be not because God is actually hiding himself, but because we have usually failed to believe that *all* that happens comes from God’s active will, as the Bible has always taught. How can God be hiding if he proclaims publicly that he is the cause of everything? If the ancient Hebrews saw God’s hand in all things, our inability to do so is due to our clouded minds, not to God’s self-concealment. The distinction we should be making, then, is not between the natural (meaning not involving God) and the supernatural (meaning he interferes with the natural), but between the natural (meaning God’s regular governance) and the irregular (in which God’s work is unpredictable).

In other words, the sole difference is between God’s sovereign choice and his gracious fidelity, and both are plainly visible in the world, unless one’s worldview blinds one to them.

10 Information, chance and choice

“We want... information.”
“You won’t get it!”

Patrick McGoohan (“The Prisoner”)

Shannon information

One of the common tools used by supporters of the Intelligent Design Movement is information theory. As was the case when I was talking about probability in a previous chapter, I am not here going to discuss how successful or otherwise ID arguments are. But one of the most interesting things about information theory is that it can teach us very little about information as we understand it in everyday life.

Two aspects of information theory are commonly used in such arguments, and I will deal in depth with neither of them, but only enough to make my points. Claude Shannon was essentially the founder of information theory, but his entire interest was in how reliably systems that convey information do so. His work is incredibly valuable in this information age, but to him “information” is simply the string of characters that goes into a transmission system, compared to what comes out of the other end. It is all one to him whether a radio transmission, say, carries a vital message in English or else a random string of meaningless digits – all that his theory deals with is the degree to which that string becomes garbled in transmission.

As such, his theory has been applied fruitfully, since DNA was first discovered, to how the genetic code is translated into living proteins, and to the mechanisms of mutation as the genome is reproduced. The earliest and most celebrated student of this field was the late Hubert Yockey, and even though some biologists deny hotly that the genetic code deals in information at all, the idea is useful in conveying to us that as far as the cellular transcription apparatus is concerned, it will translate gibberish introduced by some mad genetic scientist as readily as the natural code that produces a perfect rose. In other words, Shannon information theory has nothing whatsoever to say about the *meaning* of information.

Kolmogorov information

Another concept, called “Kolmogorov complexity” after mathematician Andrey Kolmogorov, takes us one step further, because it can be used to deal with the content of a message. It has to do with how much one can compress a message using some algorithm. This makes it of vital importance for computer science and communication technology, in which information compression plays a major role.

For example, if I send a message that reads :

”AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA”

I could shorten it to “Repeat A X20” and save bandwidth. This message has a very low Kolmogorov complexity. A more complex recurrent message, of the same length, like

“ABCABCABCABCABCABCABCABCABCABC”

could also be expressed in almost as short a manner, because of its repeating pattern, thus also exhibiting low complexity.

However, if I were to get a random number generator to produce a completely meaningless and non-repetitive string of 30 digits, there would be no way to shorten it algorithmically – the shortest form of the message would be the complete string itself. It would therefore have a *high* Kolmogorov complexity.

In effect then, Kolmogorov complexity usefully distinguishes between randomness and order, between chance and necessity. This is reflected in the physical world by the fact that, almost by definition, the scientific laws of nature are short algorithms that explain very many individual phenomena, showing what seems to be complicated in detail to be simple and ordered as a generalisation. All the matter and energy relations across the entire universe can be summed up as “ $e=mc^2$.” What is orderly and lawlike in nature, then, is distinguished by low Kolmogorov complexity. In contrast, it follows that chance events exhibit high Kolmogorov complexity. They must be described in their entirety rather than by laws or rules.

If we return to the example of tossing a coin from a previous chapter, we may well be able to take the total results of 100 throws and deduce the simple statistical law that “heads = tails (approximately).” But as I discussed earlier, each *individual* coin toss has an unpredictable outcome because the precise physical conditions of the throw are unknown, making the *sequence* of results random. To record the same series of 100 coin tosses as a sequence, then, I would have to write it out in full. The sequence displays high Kolmogorov complexity.

Another way of expressing the difference is that lawlike, or necessary, events are predictable from simple rules, whilst random events are unpredictable.

This can turn up some surprises. The astonishingly complicated looking fractal patterns first identified by Benoit Mandelbrot (such as are seen in many structures in nature), which are marked out by showing complexity at every level, are actually highly ordered. They may be generated by relatively simple computer algorithms, and so despite their visual complexity, they display low Kolmogorov complexity. Mathematically they are not at all random.

Choice and randomness

The really interesting part comes from considering a sequence of letters that we know has a meaning because it is written in English. It is full of “information” in the traditional sense, because I have carefully chosen to send an intelligible message. Does such a message, for example,

“In_the_beginning_was_the_Word!”

have a low Kolmogorov complexity (denoting order) or a high complexity (denoting randomness)?

The surprising answer is that a message with deliberate meaning is closer to randomness than it is to order. Its sequence cannot be predicted by an algorithmic rule: it must be written out in full to be understood. It has high Kolmogorov complexity.

This last point is not *absolutely* true – any particular language contains repeated letter and word patterns which, in a long passage, could be somewhat compressed: shorthand and texting language demonstrate this. But it is also probably true that there are very few “random” sequences in nature

which might also not be somewhat compressible. The surprising fact remains that intelligent choice is mathematically more like randomness than order. A poem about the beauty of a fern frond is more complex than the beauty of the fern itself. That is counter-intuitive. But it corresponds to the advice being given by security experts that computer passwords consisting of three randomly chosen words committed to memory are as secure as strings of random characters (which have to be recorded to be remembered).

At least where complicated phenomena are concerned, then, we reach the surprising conclusion that *chance is formally indistinguishable from choice*. We know that an English text is not gobbledegook *only* because we speak the same language as the writer. I could not in any way distinguish a random string of Chinese characters from a poem by Wang Wei, though a Chinese speaker could.

Consider how this principle from information theory applies to what this book is seeking to establish. It implies that any unique act of God, examined in a dispassionate, mathematical way, would be formally indistinguishable from an event arising by Epicurean chance. The only way to glean that it was indeed God's purposeful act would be to have some intelligent understanding of God's purposes, just as if he spoke a commandment in Hebrew, one would need to understand Hebrew to understand it and obey.

From the earlier chapter on the history of ideas of causation, you will recall that from ancient times human beings have been predisposed to finding purposeful meaning in natural phenomena, rather than to analyse them as orderly phenomena, as more intellectual civilisations came to do. It may be that enduing the world with such meaning was a kind of mental pareidolea, like seeing faces of the Virgin Mary in potato crisps. But on the other hand, it could also be that insistence on reducing the world to comprehensible order more or less guaranteed that its true *meaning* would inevitably be lost, simply because of how information theory works. Mediaeval Christians may have been mistaken to believe that the Black Death was a judgement from God on national sin. But they may just have forgotten less about how the world works than we have when we exclude the hand of God from COVID-19..

In the argument about the role of God in creating life, Kolmogorov complexity means that the intelligently designed genetic code of a created creature would, of necessity, appear just as incompressible and unpredictable as a randomly generated string of DNA bases. The fact that the organism is efficient, successful or beautiful could equally be explained either by belief in a good God, or by Epicurean belief that ontological chance actually exists and tends towards order... although of course, Kolmogorov complexity establishes that "order" is the polar opposite of what living things exhibit. Life isn't at all lawlike, though it is highly organised. The real Epicurean claim, in the light of information theory, is that ontological chance tends to produce not so much order as *meaning*. That is a claim far less easy to make.

Which of the two beliefs is the truth cannot be established mathematically, though, and that is why I am dubious about the viability of the Intelligent Design Movement as a purely scientific endeavour. Fortunately not all human insights come from science. Science doesn't *do* meaning, because meaning has to do with purpose and choice, not with order and certainly not with randomness. And for the very reason that science is all about discerning order, it has nothing to say about the purposeful meaning that, as we have seen, looks for all the world like randomness to information theory.

11 Chance and Freedom

*Under the bludgeonings of chance
My heady is bloody, but unbowed.*

William Ernest Henley

Creation as Pinocchio

Materialists have argued against teleology in the “laws of nature” in order both to avoid considering God, and because this renders the universe more ordered and deterministic, and therefore amenable to being fully understood by human endeavour.

Or at least, that is the theory – strong philosophical arguments have been made to show that a “theory of everything” is unachievable even in theory. In practice, the idea of science as a body of knowledge, slowly swallowing up the remainder of unclaimed ground, is false. In fact, fields of knowledge are more like islands in an infinite universe, which are usually unlikely to coalesce however much they grow. This is clear even from the way that closely-related disciplines often cannot even agree on nomenclature, let alone the significance of the same phenomena.

Another way of looking at this is that the universe is a jumble of disparate phenomena which gives incomplete answers only to the particular questions you ask it. To understand it fully you would need to ask an infinite number of such questions, and somehow integrate the answers into a single body of understanding. Such knowledge might, perhaps, make you like a god, but you would have to *be* God to ask all the right questions in the first place.

But turning away from the materialists, a relatively small number of Christians, particularly those of a scientific bent who are associated with the fashionable theology called *Open Theism* (a combination sometimes termed “Open Process Theism”), have argued against teleology in the matter of *chance* for the opposite reason. They see randomness as a way of preserving the “autonomy” and “spontaneity” of God’s creation as a kind of democracy, which prevents God’s ordaining everything “like a puppet-master.” Chance, they suggest, is the thing that preserves freedom and demonstrates God’s self-giving love. Like a parent letting go of adolescent children, a good God would surely cut the marionette-strings of the universe and give it liberty.

“Autonomy” is a word that needs careful unpacking in this context. In classical Christian teaching, there is indeed a kind of “autonomy” in nature in the sense that each part of it has its own particular “law” from God. You could view this as a particular “form” or “nature,” which may or may not overlap with the idea of scientific laws.

For example, a deer has a particular way of life from God which is very different from that of a lion: each therefore has its own (*autos*) law (*nomos*). In the inanimate realm, volcanoes, black holes or rivers all have their own “way of being” in an analogous way. In a more abstract sense, one could see something like the law of gravity as being, literally, a law unto itself by God’s decree.

When we come to human beings, we find a higher level of autonomy, in that we have the freedom to govern ourselves by God’s law (for mankind) or to disobey it, in a way that the lion and the volcano do not. We may therefore have genuine relationship with God, not to mention with each other, in a way the irrational creation cannot. I will not attempt here to plumb the incomprehensible depths of

how God's freedom and our freedom interact, except to deny either that he coerces our choices, or that our choices buck his sovereignty.

The first error of the Open Theists is to confuse those two meanings of "autonomy." We humans value freedom because we are endowed with rational choice. And we learn from the Bible that God calls us to *willing* obedience, so that in Archbishop Cranmer's words "*His service is perfect freedom.*" But to attribute a desire for that kind of freedom even to animals, let alone to stars or to abstractions like the evolutionary process (as is often done), is absurd. Indeed, the case for this idea is *always* made using emotive terms like "coercion," or "interference," or "letting nature be itself." But it is fundamentally empty and incoherent, because the irrational creation does not have a will to be enslaved or liberated.

Apparently unconsciously such writers have adopted a concept of nature that slowly developed from the Greek idea of the cosmos, in which the world became personified, "Nature" sometimes even acquiring a capital "N" or becoming an actual goddess. When we are *not* thinking great thoughts about this Nature's right to autonomy, though, we are quite happy to coerce or interfere with it without compunction ourselves. If we acted as these writers want God to do, we would have to let nature "be itself" instead of building houses or creating statues with it or eating it, as we regularly do without even asking its permission. If it is abusive for God to be a puppet-master over the universe, then it is no less abusive for a human puppeteer to control an *actual* puppet.

The Bible, our source of spiritual authority, actually presents creation as God's servant, or property, or sometimes as his household. Certainly he cares for it and considers its good, but each part of it does his bidding, without question. All but the primitive animist, who makes an offering to the spirit of the tree he cuts down, regard the world as a resource, not as a free conscious agent. And even the animist still cuts down the tree to use.

The distaste for God as controller of his creation seems to have inherited more than a little of the post-modern idea, now ubiquitous in "Critical Theory," that all relationships are power-plays involving an oppressor with all the power and an oppressed victim without power. God, the ultimate Power, even if we grant the self-emptying of Christ at the Incarnation, poses massive problems within this essentially Marxist framework, as does the Lordship of Christ.

The solutions suggested by the Open Theists thus pose insurmountable difficulties. The easiest way out of the dilemma is to use the Bible's own conceptual framework and jettison the transient secular one, however fashionable.

The kind of arguments I have made in this book so far explain how God's ordering of his servant-creation might work "on the ground," but here we can note that it is entirely *appropriate* that God should govern nature, since it was actually created for him – in Trinitarian terms it was created for Christ (Colossians 1:16). At another level, it was created for rational humanity formed in Christ's image, and is governed by God for mankind's benefit. Indeed, Psalm 104 shows that he even governs nature for its own benefit. His power is exercised in the service of his love, and is not in any way its antithesis. But creation does not operate independently of him. Nothing in Scripture teaches an autonomous nature.

The thought of nature's "right to liberty" is in some respects a moralised version of the Deist idea that God cannot interfere with the fixed laws of nature. In the latter case he would be demeaning his own glory by pushing the cogs of the cosmic clock around, and maybe cheating us humans by limiting our understanding of the clockwork. In the former he is perceived as offending the democratic rights of

entities that wouldn't, in reality, know what to do with a vote, let alone demand one. In effect, this view defines "love" as the absence of power, with the effect of maintaining the postmodern idea that everything is about power-relationships, even God's love.

God the gambler

The second error these people make is that, conditioned by the "chance and necessity" view of creation, and finding the "necessity" of the laws of nature to be deterministic and coercive (except when inconsistently asserting that God gives the laws *themselves* creaturely autonomy!), they equate "chance" with the "freedom" they advocate.

This is, once more, semantic trickery even if unconsciously so. Often the emotive case is made by using words like "spontaneity," with much recourse to images of children at carefree play or creative artists at work. In my experience this idea is closely linked with a desire to hold on to the standard Darwinian idea of evolution as undirected (depending on random or spontaneous mutations), whilst affirming the Creator God at the same time.

We have already seen that ontological randomness makes no sense in the context of biblical theism, and that there isn't actually any real place for it in science either. But if it did exist, then the very last thing it would give the world is freedom or autonomy. The idea seems to be (as far as I have found in long interaction with people who think this way) that randomness is something you *do* (or that nature does) in order to be creative and live a free and worthwhile life.

In fact, anyone who thinks about it for even a second knows that chance is something that *happens* to you, and more often than not it takes away your freedom by tripping you up, eating you, losing you money or spoiling the work you were doing.

On the rare occasions when chance provides some advantage, you might thank your lucky stars, but you won't have exercised any freedom whatsoever. That is why we refer to people as "hostages to fortune" rather than as "chance champions." Roulette players are not generally regarded as creative souls, and they are quite often pathetic victims of "Lady Luck."

Briefly to return to the concept of information theory from the last chapter, even Shannon information is defined as "the reduction of uncertainty." We deliberate, and then we determine what we desire to happen, and in so doing randomness inevitably decreases. Chance retreats before choice – it does not enable it in any way.

In fact if one accepts chance as some force beyond God's choice (in order to prevent his being all-in-all), it would be the duty of nature to clap its hands in praise of the demiurge Chance, rather than of God as the psalms describe. However one approaches it, the existence of ontological chance diminishes God and creates a rival to him, only it is a rival lacking goodness or purpose or love or justice.

We do not call a man who is completely unpredictable "free." We call him "insane."

God as Jackson Pollock

A kind of half-way house to this idea, particularly popular with those who subscribe to what is called "Evolutionary Creation," is that God "uses chance" as part of his creative repertoire, much as the artist Jackson Pollock used random paint trickles creatively.

The reasons for holding it seem to be a desire to retain the Epicurean concept of randomness which came to dominate mainstream science, as in *Chance and Necessity*, and at the same time to show how wonderfully clever God is to be able to make us even of such randomness. Simple people, they imply, think that randomness is antithetical to the role of God as the designer of all things, but that only shows their lack of imagination. Just as God can turn human evil to good, he can even turn undirected events to his purposes.

There's an element of the Houdini in this concept of God: by making creation as difficult as possible for himself, God is glorified even more when what he can't either predict or control turns out to be just what he wanted in the first place. His hands are cuffed firmly behind his back and he's underwater in a chained-up milk churn, but the next time we look we see that everything that he has made is very good, and God takes a bow.

One common example used to illustrate this is the human immune system. The first response of this system to a new pathogen is a kind of hyper-mutation process, producing a multitude of variant antibodies at random, and focusing production and refinement on whichever of them binds to the pathogen in the event. God is using randomness creatively! It is then argued that what can be demonstrated in this system in the laboratory also drives the whole creative process of evolutionary mutations, and so chance becomes one of the main tools in God's workshop.

We have already seen, though, that nothing in the process of biological mutation provides any evidence for ontological randomness. We do not know the causes of individual mutations, but God does. This is only yet another example of a failure to define what one actually means by "chance."

In any case, this example suggests that (to anthropomorphise immune cells) it is the mammalian immune system that is using what is random and unknown to itself (rather than to God) to meet new and unknown threats. Furthermore, it has worked out the trick of controlling the output of antibodies very intelligently to cover as wide a base as possible. In effect, our immune system contains a sophisticated random number generator designed for a special purpose – just as very intelligent humans have designed random number generators for our own very purposeful uses.

One can argue about whether this system was created directly by God or evolved (but I challenge you to argue for the latter without lapsing into teleological language about the purpose of the immune system!). But however it was done this is a process used by creatures of limited knowledge to make their way in the world, not by God himself. If a mammal predator engages in a random search pattern in order to pinpoint some prey to stalk, we do not thereby conclude that God doesn't know where the zebra are, even though the Bible tells us he provides the young lions with their meal.

The situation in the immune system is no different in principle from human endeavour, after all. For Ecclesiastes tells us:

*Sow your seed in the morning,
and at evening let not your hands be idle,
for you do not know which will succeed,
whether this or that,
or whether both will do equally well. (Ecclesiastes 11:6)*

Because we have limited knowledge, we have to make multiple efforts to succeed: we take chances until we strike lucky. Yet the previous verses in the chapter are an object lesson in the meaning of

epistemological randomness: the man who fails to plant because he cannot predict the weather is ignorant of what God certainly knows:

*As you do not know the path of the wind,
or how the body is formed in the womb,
so you cannot understand the work of God,
the Maker of all things. (Ecclesiastes 11:5)*

In classical theology, to say that God is omniscient is to say that he *is* all knowledge: what he does not know is not there to know. As the old theologians said, he knows all things because he knows himself perfectly, and all things come from himself. He made all things, so he made “chance” too, and to create something unknown to you is simply self-contradictory, especially when nothing exists without you.

The Open Theists quibble about this, by saying that although God knows all that may be known, the future may *not* be known, even to him, because it is not yet determined by the choices people will make (and, for those applying Open Theism to science, the choices an autonomous creation will make). Pity those who trust in promises about the future made by gods who know no more about it than they do themselves.

12 Choice and Ethics

*There is a way which seems right to a man,
But its end is the way of death.*

Proverbs 14:12

Scientific ethics

Although I am concentrating in this book mainly on science and philosophy in relation to Christian faith, the clear alternatives of a chance-necessity universe and one founded on choice-fidelity have a massive bearing on morality and ethics too. The moral and ethical framework of our society has changed dramatically over recent years, and much of that change can be attributed to the underlying shift in basic worldview I have been discussing throughout this book.

Morality generally seems to lag far behind intellectual fashions, and for a long while after the Rationalists of the Enlightenment sought to abolish God it seemed instinctive to most Western people that pure reason would follow an ethical path very similar to the Christian one, only without the superstitious dogma. Yet even back in the early 1970s Os Guinness in his Christian classic *The Dust of Death* noticed how there had been a gradual decline of biblical morality once its theistic root was cut off, and he rightly prophesied that the collapse would continue in a process he called “the striptease of Humanism.”

Since it is the case that how we do ethics dictates how we do science as well as how we do life, gaining an understanding of how this change has worked is important to Christians in all walks of life.

When I was studying Social Psychology at Cambridge, one of the lecturers was questioning whether a particular behaviour was caused by heredity, or by the environment: the old “nature *versus* nurture” debate. When I asked if it might alternatively be explained by “choice,” he replied in the negative: “It’s heredity or environment – that’s all there is.”

You will be familiar with this limited view from the argument against free will I referenced in Chapter 7, and as is obvious, like that argument it has its roots in the materialist worldview in which only chance and necessity exist as causes. In fact, in the nature-nurture debate, both of those are potentially mixtures of chance and necessity. Heredity is deterministic, but as far as individuals are concerned, their heredity is a matter of luck. Similarly, the environment is seen as conditioning behavior deterministically, but individual experiences of poverty, privilege and so on are “randomly” distributed. Choice, however, is *always* an illusion.

I’m told by those closer to the field than I am that sociology is now more open to the concept of choice, and perhaps my lecturers just happened to be more materialistic than the norm. This was, after all, only two years after *Chance and Necessity* was published. In fact, as I thought about the subject for this chapter it seemed to me that the contemporary system of ethics, which if it did not have its roots in sociology is certainly over-represented there, possesses an uneasy mixture of all three – chance, necessity *and* choice. This warrants an attempt at an explanation, since it seems to contradict my claim that the two belief systems are mutually exclusive.

The academic field of sociology, and the progressive new ethical framework that seems largely to have arisen from its writings, are deeply influenced by Marxism. Most of my social psychology

teachers were socialists, and one of my supervisors was an organizer of the infamous Garden House Riots (echoing the Paris student uprising of 1968), before his conversion to Christ.

Marxism, in turn, is deeply materialist, and indeed preened itself in the early days as the only truly scientific approach to politics and everything else that matters. The forces of history were held to be governed by inevitable laws, and individuals were the product, primarily, of the titanic and never-ending struggle between the classes. In Soviet “revolutionary justice,” which soon became enshrined in the legal system, guilt was often determined solely on someone’s having the wrong class origins, rather than any actual actions, because class was a “given” of nature which must, eventually, issue in oppressive behavior. As an old song goes:

The judge said, “Let’s kill him, before he kills some of us.”

Through a process of ideological re-thinking in the light of the failure to instigate class revolution in Western Europe, a process which involved Communists like Antonio Gramsci and the Frankfurt School, the perceived oppression was gradually shifted from the downtrodden working class to racial and sexual categories. However, these were still dealt with as classes subjected to deterministic forces of oppression *en masse* rather than as human individuals with complex motivations. There was a climax of sorts in the 1968 riots, when the students who would go on to infiltrate all the major institutions of society (according to the programme Gramsci had originally proposed) also soaked up what would become known as Postmodernism, whose epicentre was also in Paris, and which involved academics such as Michel Foucault and Jacques Derrida.

This is not the place to explore this process in detail, though it is of vital importance for Christians to have some understanding of its roots. This is because it is currently perhaps the greatest internal threat to the Church, whose own institutions have already been deeply affected by compromise with its fundamentally anti-Christian ideas.

Suffice it to note that the underlying substrate of Enlightenment determinism is what has led to the strand of progressive (or “woke” – the same word the Chinese Red Guards used of developing “class consciousness” during the Cultural Revolution) thought, that sees victimhood as an entirely passive and inevitable result for particular classes. The oppressor classes too are also both homogeneous and historically determined – one has only to consider the current theoretical category of “whiteness” to understand this. This emphasis on determinism is particularly seen in the areas of sexuality and gender.

I have no choice

Despite rather poor support from the better scientific literature, most of the minorities bundled together under the “LGBGTQ+” umbrella have gained public sympathy from the presumed inescapability of their lot. One is born somewhere – anywhere – on a spectrum of sexuality, or of gender, so nature is responsible. Even environmental “nurture” is given fairly short shrift, and “choice” is so far denied that it has become unthinkable in most circles, or even illegal, to talk about therapy to bring about change through enabling choice, even if the individual desires it. To oppose nature’s determination is the worst of evils, in this particular matter at least.

It is significant that this stress on natural “necessity” is the main argument that has been employed to convince Christians to affirm aberrant sexuality and gender roles. “If God has created this person to be gay, then it must be a good thing, and not to affirm it is to deny God’s work.” The word of God is thereby deliberately subordinated to the doctrine of necessity.

Even more doubtful as Christian thinking is, “I can’t help being a woman trapped in a man’s body,” since in this case it seems that God himself has quality control problems in his allocation of rather Cartesian, and inexplicably gendered, immaterial souls to bodies, in the absence of any evidence for physical difference from the normal.

God’s ability to do his job through his sovereign choice is, at best, severely curtailed in such thinking, once again becoming illogically subordinated to immutable natural necessity, as appears to be the case in the quotation I heard from a genetically male transsexual who said, “God created me as a woman, but my parents made me a man.” If the imposition of stereotypical “gender roles” were in mind here, it might carry some weight, but what is being said is the Creator was cheated by the parents’ choice of chromosomes. Currently, in the churches though not in the activist community, it seems that necessity did not create any paedophiles.

You have no right

The complicating factor about this, though, is that certain groups, in certain contexts, insist that their self-identity is a matter of their right to choose, as an act of inviolable human autonomy – the direct opposite of the argument from immutable nature. For example, activist groups which are accusing the churches of heartless prejudice against victims of necessity in the church setting are simultaneously arguing for the right to free choice in the political sphere. The whole phenomenon of “Pride Month,” for example, focuses on creativity in matters of gender and sexuality. It is not so much that nature generates 112 genders (taking *Tumblr’s* list more or less at random), but that human inventiveness is, and should be encouraged to be, endlessly experimental in that regard.

One of the most vivid example of “I am what I choose to be” is so-called “transracism,” in which one identifies as someone of another race. But it is not the most extreme: the minority labelling themselves “otherkins” and self-identifying as other species, real or mythical, can surely not be regarded as victims of nature’s chance or necessity: radical autonomy is the only justification this side (possibly) of insanity.

In the context of this book it is instructive to see how the admission of both “chance-necessity” and “choice” worldviews into the arena has started to cause intractable conflict within the LGBTQ+ movement. This is most clearly seen in the clash between “third wave” feminism and transsexuality, which has famously led to the “cancellation” of prominent feminists like Germaine Greer and J. K. Rowling.

To the feminists, their womanhood is a biological fact, but they maintain their ability to compete with men in every area on equal terms, as a matter of choice. To the transgender woman, however, their biology is an error and their real self is of necessity feminine in the very way the feminists are trying to escape. For women to insist that their biology matters is therefore transphobic. Or, of course, to the gender-queer proponents there are no biological realities at all, and so the feminists are mistaken to call themselves women, and so also are the transsexuals.

Needless to say something is radically mistaken in all this, but here I want only to examine how it could come about that the two fundamentally opposite worldviews I have been discussing in the book should both be so strongly represented in progressive ethics.

Part of the answer, I venture to suggest, lies in the same basic flaw in the chance-necessity system demonstrated by scientific materialists, which is that you cannot consistently live by it. However much you argue for the non-existence of the will, you will still exercise it at every point in your life.

So although the movement has its roots in Marxist materialism, the exercise of individual human will is bound to intervene – just as it did under Communist regimes, where personal malice and hatred was honed to a fine art and resulted in 100 million or more deaths, and to deeply corrupt leadership.

God has no right

But there is probably more to it than that. Both Marxism and Postmodernism are overtly *transgressive* in nature. Indeed, even Enlightenment Rationalism began by the conscious rejection of the authority of God over human choices, and the roots of this go back to the Humanist Renaissance. I explore this “Promethean” process in depth in my book *God’s Good Earth*.

Carl Trueman also traces the history of what was clearly perceived as a revolt against (the Christian) God in *The Rise and Triumph of the Modern Self*, through characters like Jean-Jacques Rousseau, the Romantic Poets Wordsworth, Shelley and Blake, Charles Darwin and Friedrich Nietzsche. Karl Marx took this hatred of all things religious further, so that atheism and the destruction of Christianity has always been a major long-term goal of Communist revolutions across the world.

In Postmodern writers like Foucault the subversion of “bourgeois” norms, especially submission to God’s rule, is also central – Foucault for example, a masochistic homosexual and an advocate of paedophilia, regarded the Marquis de Sade as one of the key figures in the modern age. And so it is no surprise that we see the “pushing of boundaries” made the supreme good in the contemporary arts, in politics and everywhere else.

So although the right to personal autonomy is insisted upon within a worldview which is basically like Monod’s (and is often incompatible with it, as we have seen), what is notably missing from it is *God’s* right to choose. This seems to me to clarify matters, because the alternative worldviews I am discussing are views about fundamental reality, and only derivatively about humanity.

In chance-necessity there is no God, and nor can there be. In choice-fidelity God is all in all, and it is only because of his sovereign will that human beings have been granted the privilege of a subordinate freedom of will. It is a fundamental of Christianity that the root of sin was not the denial of the human will, but Adam and Eve’s desire for their will to prevail over God’s, in order to “be like God.”

We have already seen in a previous chapter how the materialist reductionism of reality to laws of nature, independent of God, offered man the opportunity to discover it all and become godlike himself. Well then, although logically incompatible with that worldview, the progressive insistence on human autonomous choice plays to the same motive of rebellion against God.

This leads to a schizoid lack of rationality, particularly when it is seen in churches which, ostensibly, subscribe to the authority of God and his word. At the end of June, 2021, Britain’s Methodist Conference redrafted its marriage canon to include these words:

“The Methodist Church believes that marriage is given by God to be a particular channel of God’s grace, and that it is in accord with God’s purposes when a marriage is a life-long union in body, mind and spirit of two people who freely enter it.

“Within the Methodist Church this is understood in two ways: that marriage can only be between a man and a woman; that marriage can be between any two people. The Methodist Church affirms both understandings and makes provision in its Standing Orders for them.”

The distinctive belief of Methodists is to believe contradictory things on this – though to be fair, there are now few denominations not climbing aboard the self-contradiction train. The stance would be more credible if, along with all the other denominations apart from Quakers and Unitarians, it had not insisted, at the time that same-sex marriage became law in 2014, that it had closely examined the issues and concluded that under God, marriage must be between a man and a woman. It does you no credit to change your mind because secular society has done so and is making life difficult for your considered theological position.

It is always possible to hold contradictory views at the same time. But as is the case with the battle between feminism and transsexualism, reality will eventually bite you.

13 The Christological Creation

*Heaven above is softer blue,
Earth around is sweeter green;
Something lives in every hue
Christless eyes have never seen*

George Wade Robinson

The Hermeneutic of Love

One of the dangers of discussing nature in a philosophical, metaphysical way (as I have done by examining metaphysical concepts like “chance,” “necessity,” and “choice,”) is that God himself may become a mere metaphysical concept. Philosophically we may come to think of him only as “First Cause,” and that is not a great deal better than the scientific materialist’s “God hypothesis.” You will already realise that in this book, I am not arguing for God, but for living out the implications of a faith commitment to him.

Christianity, however, is the revelation of the Triune God, who manifested himself in human form as Jesus Christ for our redemption into a living relationship with him. That Jesus, John’s gospel tells us, is the eternal Word of God, the *Logos* by which God spoke creation into being (John 1:3). Paul expands on that by saying:

He is the image of the invisible God, the firstborn of all creation: for by Him all things were created, both in the heavens and on earth, visible and invisible, whether thrones, or dominions, or rulers, or authorities—all things have been created through Him and for Him. He is before all things, and in Him all things hold together. (Colossians 1:15-17).

That, surely, ought to have a great bearing on how Christians understand the created order, especially as we begin to think through the case for seeing divine choice, both regular and contingent, as the principles on which it operates, rather than the Epicurean concepts of chance and necessity.

When we consider God as transcendently other, which is the right way to accord him due honour and worship, we must not forget that the role of the only-begotten Son is as the mediator between the Father and creation, as well as between the Father and ourselves. Colossians 1:13-29 and 2:6-17 speak to this supremely.

Because of this, God must never be seen as incomprehensible or alien in the age of Christ’s revelation, even as he is in his Being incomprehensible. For in the first place Christ is “the exact image” of God (Hebrews 1:2-3), and secondly man is created “after the image and likeness” of God. There is a deep correspondence between mankind and its Creator that is the very antithesis of the extreme environmentalists’ “man the interloper.”

It is under this kind of consideration that we understand why the universe should be so mysteriously comprehensible – not merely because God is rational, nor because *we* are rational, but because something of the rationality of the Creator is built into his creation in general, and into the mind of man particularly. Jesus “came to his own” (John 1:11) not only because he created mankind, but because he created him after his own image and likeness.

The question, then, of how we could possibly recognise God or his work in nature is answered by replacing the illusory “objective view from nowhere” with the more truthful concept that we view the world as beings created in the image of the true Image of God. We are not self-made creatures reaching out to an alien God, but were, in fact, created both by and for him. Christ is in our DNA (metaphorically and, in some sense, even literally). This correlation between Christ and man through creation can also explain the “unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics” (in physicist Eugene Wigner’s phrase) in science, but not, I would suggest, because mathematics is the language of God, as Galileo once said – though it might indeed be his machine code.

N. T. Wright has done some excellent thinking on this, for example in his Gifford lectures in 2018. Because “nature” is actually “Christ’s nature,” Wright describes a “hermeneutic of love” in understanding the world, arising inevitably from the revelation of the new creation in Christ that also makes sense of the old. He goes on to make this the basis for a biblical natural theology (discovering God through nature), but we could – or perhaps must – equally take it as the basis for a theology of nature itself (how we understand nature because of God). How can a theology of nature be adequate if it does not arise from the revelation of Christ, its Creator? In particular (Wright insists) it cannot possibly be adequate if it arises instead from the prevalent Epicurean philosophy of our culture.

Incidentally, Wright disarms the accusation of “subjectivity” in this approach by pointing out that love is the fundamental reality of the universe, whereas “objectivity” is simply a convenient illusion based on a particular ancient philosophy. Like me, he sees faith in Christ as turning our view of things upside down – or rather, the right way up. Even the hostile Jews in Thessalonica recognised that was the implication of the gospel (Acts 17:6).

So we do not develop a theology of nature primarily as a basis for science: rather we seek to understand nature in relation to God. It’s just that if science wishes to be on the same page as nature, it will have to be based on the best theology of nature available. Remember that Francis Bacon’s new science, the science we have inherited, was based on the best theology he knew back in the seventeenth century, leading to the enduring concept of divine laws, amongst many other things. Unless we believe that the success of his scientific programme was merely accidental, improving that theology can only change science for the better.

Logos and Language

It is not that this emphasis has always been lacking in Christian thought. I have already quoted the quantum pioneer Werner Heisenberg, whose Christian approach to understanding the world was in its own way as profound as Wright’s. In his *Physics and Philosophy* he noted how the *meaning* of nature – which we have identified as Christ – became lost in science’s progress, to our great loss:

However, the emphasis on experience was connected with a slow and gradual change in the aspect of reality. While in the Middle Ages what we nowadays call the symbolic meaning of a thing was in some way its primary reality, the aspect of reality changed toward what we can perceive with our senses. What we can see and touch became primarily real....

...At the same time the human attitude toward nature changed from a contemplative one to a pragmatic one. One was not so much interested in nature as it is; one rather asked what one can do with it...

But in Jesus, the divine Word or *Logos*, Heisenberg sees a strong link between understanding the universe and speech – even human speech, that Kolmogorov-complex mystery that conveys meaning

whilst looking random. The nature of the world is then, in Heisenberg's view, an interconnected network of meaning, at multiple levels. Meaning, purpose, and interconnectedness are the nature of reality, and are not just a human epiphenomenon as materialists believe. The mediaevals (and in fact all earlier cultures) were right to recognise this, and to attempt to build their worldview upon decoding it.

The difference for us now, since the Incarnation, is that in Christ we have the right key, the mystery hidden from ages past, as Wright unpacks in his Gifford lectures. Christ's meaning permeates the whole of nature – and of course, that must include his teleological purposes for it. Choice is primary because Christ is the Creator.

Heisenberg is remarkably bold about this, considering his secular reputation as a Nobel physicist. He argues that modern physics itself demands a wider outlook than the old materialism allows for the relationship between the human mind and reality. Quantum physics and relativity themselves, he reasons, point to the fact that “natural language” (with its intimate connection to the *Logos* of God), rather than mathematics, is the true language of nature. Mathematics is great for valid generalisations, but not for the reality in which meaning is found:

Furthermore, one of the most important features of the development and the analysis of modern physics [is] that the concepts of natural language, vaguely defined as they are, seem to be more stable in the expansion of knowledge than the precise terms of scientific language, derived as an idealization from only limited groups of phenomena. This is in fact not surprising since the concepts of natural language are formed by the immediate connection with reality; they represent reality... On the other hand, the scientific concepts are idealizations; they are derived from experience obtained by refined experimental tools, and are precisely defined through axioms and definitions. Only through these precise definitions is it possible to connect the concepts with a mathematical scheme and to derive mathematically the infinite variety of possible phenomena in this field. But through the process of idealization and precise definition the immediate connection with reality is lost. The concepts still correspond very closely to reality in that part of nature which had been the object of the research. But the correspondence may be lost in other parts containing other phenomena.

Another way of looking at this, in keeping with my overall theme, is that mathematics can express the fidelity of God in the regular operations of the world, but only “natural language” can find the meaning of those “random” events which, I have argued, ultimately relate to God's free choices. Or, as we have now briefly explored, they relate to the choices of the Eternal Son who now rules his own creation at the right hand of the Father, in keeping with the same love that took him to the cross for our sake.

I suggest you take some time out to meditate on that.

14 Doing Science with Choice

I commence a sacred discourse, a most true hymn to God the Founder, and I judge it to be piety, not to sacrifice many hecatombs of bulls to him and to burn incense of innumerable perfumes and cassia, but first to learn myself, and afterwards to teach others too, how great he is in wisdom, how great in power, and of what sort in goodness.

Johannes Kepler

Novum Organum

Heisenberg's words in the last chapter show that "Theology can seriously affect your science." That chapter touched on some very deep issues, and I will address even deeper issues before the end of the book, if only to remind us that the only appropriate attitude we should have before the universe, and even more before God, is humility. "There is a God, and you are not him."

But from the outset of writing this book, I have had in mind my own professional scientific background, and that of the many people I have interacted with in the sciences over the years. I want the book to inform all who care to read it, but I also want it to be a relatively simple introduction to useful ideas for those whose bread and butter is the profession of science.

To them I want to say that for the vast majority of scientists, my suggested re-formulation of nature at the "metaphysical" level need not affect their work in the least. It may be less true in fields like quantum physics, if Heisenberg is to be believed, but that is certainly above my pay-grade as a humble medic. But for most sciences, "choice and fidelity" can in practice be interchanged with "chance and necessity" without altering even one's working vocabulary, let alone one's practice. All it changes is your entire view of the meaning of what you discover (so in that important sense the health warning that it can "seriously affect your science" still stands).

This matters because the practice of science is a human institution with its own community and conventions, which can be universally pursued across cultures, languages and religious divides freely and without favour. It would be a pity if a more biblical understanding of physical reality were to exclude you from the company of those others who dedicate their lives to investigating it.

That, at least, is the ideal, although in recent years the ideal has been seriously tarnished in a number of fields by pressures from governments, corporations and idealists of one persuasion or another. The damage done to the scientific process during the COVID crisis has sadly demonstrated that. I can see that within my own erstwhile profession it has become harder to perform the best medicine without suffering a degree of alienation from professional institutions and colleagues, and I hope these are not signs of a serious decline in the value of the scientific enterprise.

If nothing else, doing science as the study of the actions of God is a constant reminder to scientists of their accountability beyond this life to the same Lord whose works they are supposed to be illuminating. Even church leaders can become corrupt, but self-justification is more difficult to achieve whilst you know you are accountable to God.

There is no reason, however, why my proposal in this book should add to conflict or corruption in science in any way, not even to the degree that the Intelligent Design Movement has been viewed as grit in the oyster rather than part of the club (though that movement's dissidence has forced scientists to do some serious thinking they might otherwise have neglected).

Remember, therefore, how we have modified the concepts of chance and necessity from their Epicurean meaning.

Chance, as we have said, is properly used in science to mean “of unknown cause,” and that is the definition I have retained. I have drawn attention to the fact that reading Epicurean “ontological randomness” into that definition has always been invalid *as science*, and it would be equally invalid to read “divine choice” into it when doing science. But why would anyone think such a metaphysical commitment is permissible in scientific writing? In any case, the Christian recognizes that in many cases, “random” events may have regular causes under the laws of nature.

And so whilst using the same term “randomness,” the materialist is free to understand it as uncaused chance, the theist as divine choice, and the pantheists, panentheists, Hindus or Wiccans as whatever they choose. They will argue about it over coffee, but not, except illegitimately, at conferences.

Necessity, when it is used in science at all, implies only that some lawlike process is universally observed to apply to some phenomenon. In this secondary sense the Christian has no problem with it, for it represents the faithfulness of God in his government of the universe. That government is at least as consistent, that is to say as necessary, as any law of nature, especially since the whole concept of laws of nature was intended to express that very faithfulness by Bacon and his followers.

At the level of philosophy of science, I have argued that the idea of “laws” has some problems. But whilst it remains the standard approach to doing science, it is perfectly serviceable to both Christians and unbelievers. If some new Aristotelian paradigm were ever to replace laws with substantial forms, that too would be fine: the only difference between Christians and Materialists would be whether God or some primary Necessity created the forms, which is another discussion for the pub, not the publications.

Nothing else, as far as I can see, is altered in the practice of science.

Choosing Fidelity

If a believing scientist is concerned that the metaphysical differences I have laid out are themselves enough to cause alienation from unbelieving colleagues, or to affect their professional standing in any way, I would respectfully point out that the Christian is *supposed* to differ from the unbeliever in the most fundamental truths. How one deals with the difficulties of living the truth in a hostile world are problems of discipleship every individual has to resolve. Do I refuse to take part in sacrifices and orgies with my trade guild, or do I give up my career? Do I denounce the Jews I know to the Gestapo, or do I risk my own arrest? In neither of these cases is it a faithful Christian option to become a pagan or a Nazi myself to avoid conflict.

On the other hand many scientists find themselves rather isolated in their own churches. Actually they are not alone in that – no church has that many artists, traffic wardens or merchant bankers, either. The problems scientific folk may suffer in church include suspicion of evolution if you’re in biology, suspicion over ethical problems if you’re in medicine, suspicion of not being green if you’re an oil geologist, and so on.

But many of the conflict risks in churches arise from the perception that science has ousted God from his rightful place. In some cases these suspicions are grounded, when believing scientists themselves have failed to develop a truly Christian theology of nature, and instead have absorbed the materialist

zeitgeist of the majority of their colleagues. If you argue for materialism in a church setting, you deserve some kickback.

Getting the fundamentals right solves the problem of trying to live between two worlds: one can be a fully paid-up scientist in the lab, and without shifting mindsets, a fully biblical Christian in the church.

More than that, to the extent that many scientifically-lay Christians have themselves been infected by the Epicurean virus, the thinking scientist is in a position to help ordinary Christians – and even interested outsiders – bridge the gap between their faith and natural science. So when someone in your house group says that he knows it's pointless praying about earthquakes because such things “just happen” (and so prays only that the rescue-workers will be blessed), there will be teaching opportunities aplenty on how God interacts with his world – even though it means you will have to work a bit harder on the theology of “natural evil.” It ought to be Christian scientists, who work with nature every day, who lead the discussion on divine action in the world, rather than being the ones attributing everything to “natural” causes.

The Extent of God's Choice

Before ending this chapter, I want to address one issue not unrelated to this – that of what is called “meticulous providence.” If God has a direct interest in all events, as I have argued here, this certainly raises issues of “theodicy” (justifying God's actions). In my book *God's Good Earth* I have argued that Scripture plainly tells us that *why* God does things is his business, not ours (as Francis Bacon rightly recognized). *That* he does them, or does not prevent them, it teaches with great certainty.

There is, though, another problem which people have with meticulous providence, and that is the accusation that it makes God a micro-manager, which in human organisations is a sign of insecurity and poor leadership. This ought to remind us of the “puppet-master” accusations of the Open Theists, which are designed to encourage an emotional reaction rather than serious theology.

Thomas Aquinas dealt fully with the “micro-manager” accusation many centuries ago, basically by pointing out that a human governor is fundamentally different from the Creator and Sustainer of all things. Who knew that? Speaking directly of why human micro-managers act as they do (without using the modern term) he says:

... as a matter of fact, this is so because of his own deficiency ... Now, deficiencies of this kind are far removed from God, because He knows all singular things, and He does not make an effort to understand, or require any time for it; since, by understanding Himself He knows all other things, as we showed above. Therefore, He plans even the order for all singular things. So, His providence applies to all singulars immediately.

Why should God be interested even in the tiny details, the “singulars,” of creation? Well for one thing even human beings are, so why would God have a lesser view? There are humans who study the entire cosmos, and others whose interest is in individual subatomic particles, even though we ourselves occupy a scale far removed from either. In fact, your reading of this book shows that your own interest encompasses both extremes in a single mind.

But also, providence is meticulous because God is, in Christian doctrine, immense, which means not “huge” but “beyond measurement.” King Solomon asked God to dwell in the temple he had built, even though he knew the highest heaven could not contain him. If he is immense in this way, there is no valid scale by which to measure him. So on what possible basis would he be more concerned with

events at one scale than another, seeing that he created them all from nothing? It really is no more problematic for God literally to number all the hairs on our head than it is for him to create the galaxies. Indeed, the real problem would be to understand how he would leave to chance what even we care deeply about.

And this is, surely, absolutely consistent with what science reveals of the regularities God orders. Is it not the case that electrons and galaxies obey the very same laws, and that the gravity that holds the entire universe together operates by exactly the same mathematics at the atomic level? This bespeaks God's interest in his Creation at all scales, even if the Bible did not teach it in as many words.

God's choices, then, operate wherever you look in the universe, simply because science operates wherever you look. Like fractal patterns, God is equally present at all levels. And science, as we have seen, tracks God's choices, whether those choices are regular or contingent.

But if you are disposed to disagree, you need to give an answer to what controls any particular phenomenon in nature, if not God's disposing will? The answer will have to be Monod's chance and necessity.

15 Behold, I show you a mystery

*The heavens tell of the glory of God;
And their expanse declares the work of His hands.
Day to day pours forth speech,
And night to night reveals knowledge.*

Psalm 19:1-2

We saw in Chapter 13 how the God whose choices guide and sustain the universe is also the God who spoke it into being by his eternal Word, and that Word is the Son whom Christians serve as Lord and Saviour. The introduction of the Letter to the Hebrews also reminds us of the closeness of the connection between creation and saving revelation:

God, after He spoke long ago to the fathers in the prophets in many portions and in many ways, in these last days has spoken to us in His Son, whom He appointed heir of all things, through whom He also made the world. Hebrews 1:1

The drawing of this connection is not simply a New Testament insight. Psalm 19, quoted at the top of this chapter, uses the eloquence of the creation concerning God's wisdom and glory to set the stage for a parallel section extolling the perfection, and the eternal endurance, of the written Law of Yahweh.

This is what led many Christians, over many centuries, to employ the metaphor of God's two books, that of nature and that of Scripture. Francis Bacon himself was one who stated that idea overtly, implying that both are sources of divine revelation in different ways, rather than being merely the overflowing of God's power and wisdom to be found out by us (nature being explored stumblingly by science, and revelation by the fallible Scripture authors themselves). Revelation is, we must stress, always about effective *communication*, by the supreme Author of communication, the *Logos*.

From the Bible we come to realise that because of Christ there is a more-than-fortuitous relationship between mankind and its Creator. This occurs at more than one level. It is not because we just happen to be generically intelligent, as God is intelligent (likewise for any other quality), that we can conceive, and even relate to, God. It is because we ourselves are created with specific affinities to God, and because the whole creation is, as much as anything else about it, God's revelation of himself to us to enable us in our image-bearing. In that sense, creation was made for man, though that doesn't preclude its having entirely different purposes as well.

This is what explains the extraordinary intelligibility of the universe, to which Albert Einstein famously drew attention in *Physics and Reality*:

The most incomprehensible thing about the universe is that it is comprehensible.

It is not simply that God satisfies his creativity through creation, and that we can teach ourselves, through science or maths or meditation, to find truths about him from it. Rather the "two book" analogy only acquires its validity from the concept of *revelation* – we read what God has written in nature, because he actually wrote it so we could read it, and so give him glory and praise for his works. What we may learn about God from science is limited (see Romans 1:20) but real. One seldom explored aspect of that is what the very nature of scientific reality itself reveals, that is to say our theme of divine choice.

It ought not to surprise us that a number of great scientists have wondered about these deep issues and have come to surprisingly theological conclusions about the very nature of nature, beyond the rather agnostic and rarified hints of Einstein.

One such example is the astronomer and physicist Arthur Eddington, who first championed the German Einstein to a suspicious British science community as the First World War ended, and was one of the first to understand quantum theory. A century ago he brilliantly argued, in a book called *The Nature of the Physical World* that, the “solid reality” of materialism is actually even less secure than the chance and necessity which Epicureans believe give rise to it.

Eddington begins his case by showing how different is the world of our experience – summed up in a careful description of his desk and its surroundings – from the mysterious underlying world of electrons, fields and quantum events, discovered by science, that describe his desk scientifically. Whatever we find in our normal world turns out, on close investigation, to be something else. Apparent solids are actually tiny particles of energy that are also waves occupying a miniscule proportion of empty space. In the fundamental quantum world even normal causality is dubious.

It is this difference between the macro-world and what science uncovers that has led materialists to downplay the perceived world, and to emphasize that the “real” world is what is described in the equations or detected with instruments. In fact all we know of that deeper world is, as Eddington puts it, “pointer readings”: but does that make it a more truthful reality?

We know our consciousness is real – but we have to take it on trust from our senses that the world outside our minds is what it seems to be. And science has shown us that if we drill down, it isn't. Our reality turns out to be generated by energy pulses called quanta that bear no clear relationship to our perceived world.

Yet building carefully on the foundation that the one reality we know for sure is our consciousness, Eddington comes to the conclusion that the fundamental truth in the universe is mind – both God's mind and our minds – and that the intuitive world of desks and dogs trees we inhabit is the closest thing to reality we have, albeit of rather shadowy substance. The world of the particles comes a distant third:

The mystic, if hauled before a tribunal of scientists, might perhaps end his defence on this note. He would say: 'The familiar material world of everyday conception, though lacking somewhat in scientific truth, is good enough to live in; in fact the scientific world of pointer readings would be an impossible sort of place to inhabit. It is a symbolic world and the only thing that could live comfortably in it would be a symbol.'

My conception of my spiritual environment is not to be compared with your scientific world of pointer readings; it is an everyday world to be compared with the material world of familiar experience. I claim it as no more real and no less real than that. Primarily it is not a world to be analysed, but a world to be lived in.'

A simple analogy to his thinking might be the familiar television. View its screen minutely and randomly scintillating pixels are revealed. Explore the workings minutely and a whole world of electronic phenomena and digital pulses is discovered, all conforming to the complexities of Shannon's information theory and Kolmogorov complexity which TV engineers and broadcasters have painstaking developed over the years.

But has that exploration revealed the fundamental truths about television? Surely not, for the purpose of the whole hardware and infrastructure is the communication of human ideas – not that 21st century television networks necessarily convey that many worthwhile ideas. But the principle is clear enough.

I find it fascinating that Eddington's assault on the reality of the material world ends up making it, for all that, a worthwhile home for us to live in, a home given to us by God. I find it even more fascinating that Eddington is far from alone amongst scientists in such an anti-materialist position.

Werner Heisenberg too, having been a pioneer in the discovery of quantum physics, similarly concludes that the most important, primary reality of the world is the world we see about us, the world of people and things. To much of this he suspects that the "fundamental" laws of physics, even quantum physics, might not apply – which in the context of this book might be understood in terms of the superimposition of God's "choice" on his "fidelity." That is a bold notion for a Nobel prizewinner to entertain.

In Heisenberg's case, as we have already seen in previous chapters, he is fascinated by the close link between actual reality and the spoken language. The Bible too, as we have also seen, links the creation of reality closely to language spoken by God, whether one considers the powerful "word of the Lord" in Hebrew (*dabar*), which accomplishes what it describes, or its incarnation as Jesus the *Logos* in the New Testament.

It is as if Heisenberg sees this world less as a cosmos of physical things, and more as a kind of authorized communication between the mind of God and the minds of people. It is the meeting of minds that is the truly fundamental feature of creation.

What Eddington and Heisenberg address through contemplation of physics, William Dembski addresses from the newer viewpoint of information, in a book called *Being as Communion*. He wrote this more as a Christian philosopher than as an Intelligent Design proponent. Matter, he argues, cannot give a complete account of information, and matter itself can only be inferred from the informational "signatures" of the particular forms it takes. Information explains matter, but not *vice versa*, and therefore information is prior.

When we do science, we don't encounter matter in its raw state nor do we encounter sensory experiences in their raw state. Rather, we encounter certain patterns to the exclusion of others. In other words, we encounter information. The material and sensory features associated with those patterns are secondary. Indeed, those very features are themselves patterned and thus informational. The patterns, or equivalently the types of information conveyed, are primary.

Like the other two writers Dembski notes how that information is invariably mediated to us as physical human beings:

We are forced to give up the notion of pure, unadulterated information from the world. Better to think of observational information not simply as given by nature but as actively taken by the observer in an activity that is guided by the theories, beliefs and concepts in the mind of the actor.

It is only purely subjective minds which may interpret what God's subjective mind created. The actual reality between these two minds appears to be, in effect, only a medium like the television's digital pulses, however worthy of investigation such things are in their own right.

If in this way “*observation trades in appearances, not in reality,*” it would appear that the real underlying nature of things lies in a communication of *meaning* between the mind of God as Creator, and the minds of humans as those in his image. If we remind ourselves that the source of that communication is Jesus the Word, then it is a communication of love. Whatever “the real world” is it is primarily a medium of communication between minds – purposeful communication. We need not exclude from this conclusion the reality not only of other human minds than our own, but of angelic minds, and the minds of animals in their various degrees.

Such profound ideas are not limited to the age of relativity, quantum physics or information theory. Even three centuries ago the philosopher George Berkeley explored similar ground, culminating in his denial that there is anything very definite one can say about matter at all. That led him to put mind, or “spirit”, at the centre of things and to deny the necessity for matter’s “real” existence altogether.

Now one might decide Berkeley has taken things too far in abolishing matter from his cosmology, but it is important to realise that he was not saying that the world we experience does not exist. On the contrary reality is solid enough, but not because it is made of something called matter, but because the far more solid reality of God communicates truthfully with the solid reality of our minds through a solid reality of ideas.

When one considers that Christian doctrine teaches that it is God the eternal Spirit who not only created all things, but who through Christ “*the radiance of His glory and the exact representation of His nature ... upholds all things by the word of His power*” (Hebrews 1:3), it is actually quite hard to imagine what he would be sustaining other than such a communication between minds.

Ideas like this seem mind-stretching and even preposterous. But upon reflection even the impression that they are “well out there” may be a product of our inherited materialism. In fact, it rather looks as though such thinkers, including some of our greatest scientists, have come back full-cycle to the way our ancestors thought about things.

Do you remember those Babylonian priests reading omens that were more significant as decrees of the gods than as physical phenomena? Do you remember the Egyptian tomb-paintings in which the phenomena of the physical realm were, in reality, the substance of deities? Those ancestors include the inspired writers of our Bible, for whom Yahweh “*makes the winds His messengers, Flaming fire His ministers*” (Psalm 104:4).

The reality of our minds and our ability to choose: these are undeniable. The reality of God’s mind and his ability to choose: of this there is no question to those with faith. But the reality of material things independent of minds? Now that has a somewhat shakier foundation. Furthermore it is frankly less important, except insofar as those material things – whatever they actually are in their true nature – serve the purposes of their Creator.

Or to put it another way, they are less important except insofar as they express God’s choice, and God’s fidelity.